

The transformative power of legal pluralism? Planetary challenges in a diverse and multi-polar world

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Panel 1

Establishing Culturally Relevant Fact and Opinion Evidence: A Dialogue between Forensic and Expert Social Anthropology and the Law

Convenors: James W. W. Rose, The University of Melbourne (james.rose@unimelb.edu.au); Mariana Monteiro de Matos, Max Planck Institute for Social Anthropology (monteirodematos@eth.mpg.de); Rusalina Idrus, Universiti Malaya (rusaslina@um.edu.my)

Legal professionals working in pluralistic intercultural jurisdictions regularly encounter three distinctive challenges when considering the evidence of culturally diverse parties. The first challenge is to identify and to brief appropriately qualified forensic investigators who are competent to discover culturally relevant fact evidence. The second challenge is to identify and to brief appropriately qualified expert witnesses who are competent to provide expert opinion and advice. The third challenge is to ensure that all parties to intercultural proceedings achieve equitable access to justice. In response to these challenges, an expanding community of social anthropologists backed by the UK-based Royal Anthropological Institute, has developed a specialized branch of their field termed 'forensic and expert social anthropology' (FESA). FESA is specifically adapted to assist legal professionals in delivering integrated forensic investigative and expert opinion and advice services relevant to intercultural proceedings. FESA utilizes a body of legally coherent social scientific theory, methodology, and justice-oriented ethical standards geared towards cooperation between social anthropology and the law.

Accordingly, the panel convenors invite papers from legal professionals, social anthropologists, sociolegal scholars, as well as parties themselves, who are familiar with the challenges of establishing culturally relevant fact and opinion evidence in intercultural legal settings. The convenors are especially interested to hear from presenters based in either the Global North or South on the legal challenges of achieving equitable access to justice for parties who may be culturally marginalized within national populations. Such parties may include Indigenous and Afro-descendant peoples, peasants, the working poor, migrants, internally displaced persons, asylum seekers, and others.

Decolonizing Expert Evidence in the Inter-American Human Rights System? A Dialogue between Law and Social Anthropology

Dr Mariana Monteiro de Matos, Postdoc fellow, Federal University of Para, Brazil; Research associate, Max Planck Institute for Social Anthropology, Germany, monteirodematos@eth.mpg.de

The role of socio-anthropological expert evidence in judicial settings has been a topic of long-standing debate in the interdisciplinary field of law and social anthropology. With the emergence of human rights and related protection mechanisms monitored by international bodies, this debate has taken on new contours and faced new challenges. Chief among these is translating the identity markers of traditional peoples, which are embedded in local knowledge, for judges and legal professionals from foreign countries who are not familiar with the actual contexts of rights disputes. At the inter-American level, social anthropologists acting as experts have begun to advocate for the alignment of expert reports with the interests of the communities in question. This objective is to be achieved through methodological approaches, such as collaborative research, with the final goal of enhancing the right to self-determination

and, in particular, the political autonomy of Indigenous peoples. A fundamental yet often overlooked issue in the existing literature is the role of colonialism and its vestiges in the *modus operandi* of international human rights law. In addressing this gap, this research explores decolonial approaches for producing evidence under the Inter-American System in environmental complaints involving Indigenous peoples. It adopts an interdisciplinary perspective, based on the analysis of case law, primary documentary sources, and a review of socio-anthropological literature. This paper aims to contribute to the continued dialogue between forensic and social anthropology and the law on ethnicity, diversities, and the *derecho a la diferencia* (literally, right to difference).

The Role of Forensic and Expert Social Anthropology in Implementing Australia's Aboriginal Sacred Sites Act

Dr. James Rose

Senior Fellow, The University of Melbourne, Australia, james.rose@unimelb.edu.au

Between the 1970s and 1990s, Australia implemented various pieces of legislation at federal, state, and territory levels intended to safeguard the viability of Aboriginal culture. Among these, the NT Aboriginal Sacred Sites Act 1989 (NTASSA) is designed to regulate the impact of capital works and land-use on Aboriginal places of religious worship in the Northern Territory. Among six jurisdictions comprising Australia's federation, the Northern Territory is home to the largest proportion of Aboriginal Australians, who are otherwise culturally marginalized within the national population. The NTASSA establishes a statutory authority named the Aboriginal Areas Protection Authority (AAPA), and empowers it to enforce the Act through a combination of administrative procedures and litigation. Although the NTASSA does not explicitly mention social anthropologists, they have come to play integral roles under the terms of the Act by investigating the locations, extents, and cultural significance of sacred sites, and by providing opinion and advice on site protection in cooperation with Aboriginal custodians. In these roles, social anthropologists perform two sets of forensic and expert functions involving both the provision of investigative services, and opinion and advice services. Through their collaboration with statutory officers and legal professionals, social anthropologists employed by the AAPA have consequently become important contributors to legal pluralism and intercultural justice in the Northern Territory. This paper describes the forensic and expert roles and functions of social anthropology as deployed by the AAPA, and the relevance of social anthropologists' specialized training, study, and experience for intercultural justice more broadly.

Proof of Peninsular Malaysia Orang Asli Customary Land Rights at Common Law: Challenges and Opportunities

Rusaslina Idrus, Senior Lecturer, Faculty of Arts and Social Sciences; Associate, Centre for Malaysian Indigenous Studies, Universiti Malaya; rusaslina@um.edu.my

Yogeswaran Subramaniam, Advocate and Solicitor, High Court of Malaya; Associate, Centre for Malaysian Indigenous Studies; yoges_s@yahoo.com

Peninsular Malaysia's Indigenous minority, the Orang Asli, do not enjoy express statutory protection and recognition of their customary lands and territories. However, the Malaysian courts have consistently recognized their common law land rights since 1996. For more than two decades, this recognition has provided an avenue for affected Orang Asli communities to seek justice through litigation in response to increased displacement from their customary territories. This paper focuses on issues arising from the evidential requirement for Orang Asli customary land claimants to prove their "aboriginality" and traditional and cultural connection to the claimed land, usually with supporting evidence from an expert knowledgeable in social anthropology. Doctrinally, these requirements reaffirm existing power

imbalances and legal hierarchies, risk distorting local cultural realities during their translation into a form relevant to the legal process and can potentially change the extent of legally recognizable customary territories. In practice, there still appears to be a distinct lack of resources, readiness and support to cater for this specialized form of civil litigation and its actors, suggesting that equitable access to justice for the Orang Asli in this regard remains a low priority for the government. Notwithstanding these challenges, it is suggested that there remain opportunities for social anthropologists to utilize both the law and legal arena to centre the value of Indigenous knowledge and connections to land, and challenge more static notions of Indigenous culture and tradition.

Delimitation and Demarcation of Native Customary Lands: Interfacing Legislation, Native Law and Customs in Sarawak

Ramy Bulan, faculty of law, University of Malaya, ramy@um.edu.my

In the modern nation state, indigenous customary tenures based on adat cannot be discussed in isolation from state law as each impacts the other. This paper discusses the practical challenges in the interface of land legislation and native law and customs in the context of creation of native communal reserves, land demarcations as the state attempts to accommodate the demands of communal and individual rights under native laws and customs. This requires accurate contemporary ethnographic data for implementation. As a system based on the Torrens system of registration under the Sarawak Land Code, all lands without title is defined as state land, but the Code also provides for recognition of customary tenure based on personal customary laws of the native persons and communities. This is a contradiction in terms. It underscores the fact that a full grasp of the plurality of applicable laws and equitable access to justice demands an understanding of the historical, political, economic, and social realities.

Panel 2 Customary Law in Nontraditional Settings

Convenors: Sandra Joireman, University of Richmond, sjoirema@richmond.edu and Janine Ubink, Van Vollenhoven Institute for Law, Governance and Society, Leiden University, j.m.ubink@law.leidenuniv.nl

Customary law is deeply rooted in societies, establishing norms of behavior and control over resources. It is often associated with rural areas in the Global South where it is administered by customary leaders to control access to land, water, and common property. However, the embedded practices of customary law are not limited to rural areas or control over natural resources. Wherever people migrate, they carry customary law with them in their family practices, traditions, and choices. Scholars have long been aware of the way that certain customary cultural practices, such as dowry and bride price, travel with people outside their home communities to urban areas and elsewhere; surviving through changed circumstances and increases in wealth, well-being, and education. Yet we also see customary legal practices in other settings: slum communities within and outside of urban areas, refugee camps, and cities in the Global North. In all these places we can see customary law practiced across generations and geographic (dis)location. This panel seeks to highlight the places and spaces outside of traditional settings where we see customary law and practices. Papers are welcome that address:

- specific customary practices in nontraditional settings;
- the reasons people choose to bring customary law into these settings;
- the understandings and interpretations given to customary practices in nontraditional settings;
- the ways in which customary practices in nontraditional settings create new economic and political opportunities;
- hybridities and interlegalities resulting from the meeting of customary law and statute law in nontraditional settings;
- and other related contributions.

The Birthing and Alignment of Theories: Separate, Equal but Interdependent

Dr Rebecca Emiene Badejogbin, Council of Legal Education, Nigerian Law School,
badejogbin_re@yahoo.com

Sub-Saharan Africa's unique legal systems due to colonialism have developed into plural legal systems in the postcolonial context, which makes inevitable the aligning and interactions of diverse legal systems and consequently their underlining legal theories. Although these theories were birthed in the studies of western and medieval societies, the systems under which they apply have become the dominant legal systems in sub-Sahara Africa, whether in actuality or seemingly despite the recognition of legal pluralism. However, the dearth of theories that sustain the application of indigenous laws still are a challenge. One instance is the positivist concept of law where H L A Hart in his analysis erroneously excluded indigenous laws. The implication of this for indigenous law is that legal doctrines such as judicial discretion, which Hart developed in the purview of positivism in its application by the courts, may stymie the ascertainment and application of indigenous law by the courts. Based on empirical data, this paper presents a theoretical basis to address this. The theoretical impasse in Hart's concept of law and its analysis of judicial discretion must be addressed to build a theoretical bridge where indigenous law can survive and be developed. The convergence and interactions of these plural systems and their theoretical basis must accommodate, in pragmatic ways, and enhance the peculiarity of the plural African systems of law in a post-colonial context.

Law in Global and Hybrid Spaces

Annett Bochmann, Humboldt University Berlin, annett.bochmann@hu-berlin.de

The presentation provides insights into how legal orders are established in spaces where state law is absent. I argue that refugee camps in the Global South, often discussed as sites of legal limbo and states of exception, are not spaces devoid of law. Rather, they initially appear to be global and hybrid spaces of legal pluralism and entanglement, where international law, state law, and other forms of law merge. However, when observing local legal practices in great detail and the living law, this pluralism is dissolved into a powerful local camp law. This characteristic type of legal order is produced by social camp-specific mechanisms, camp materiality, and the remaking of local law practiced in the regions of origin. Therefore, I argue that refugee camps should be viewed as extraterritorial spaces with a high degree of legal autonomy that enables and forces residents to create a local camp law. However, this specific legal situation described here is not easily transferable to refugee camps and other extraterritorial spaces around the globe. It is only possible to understand how law is made in such spaces by carrying out detailed and long-term ethnographic studies of local orders and the living law. The findings of the study contribute not only to the literature on law and order in camps but also to the debates on plural and hybrid configurations in extraterritorial and neocolonial spaces.

Public health administration in Switzerland - a legal pluralistic case study on psychotherapy and psychotherapeutic training services

Markus Weilenmann, Office for Conflict Research, Zurich-Rüschlikon, Switzerland,
markusweile@conflictresearch.ch

Switzerland, an economic very prosperous Confederation in the heart of Western Europe, harbors a great variety of different therapeutic treatments to address mental health diseases. Due to its federal political system with strong political communities and cantons (states) and with a much weaker political center stage at the national level than its neighboring countries Austria, France, Germany

or Italy, the national welfare state developed later but steadily and smoothly. Only in the late 1990ies, its public health administration got into more controversial scrutiny, mainly because of the introduction of a national health insurance system, which is statutorily based on individual provisions and administered by competing private health insurance companies. In addition, the hospital services are financed by the different cantons resp. by their individual tax collecting system. But due to regional income disparities and other economic variations, the rates for the private health insurance companies as well as the financial resources and capacities of the cantons differ and not all private companies and cantons dispose of similar financial resources to cover their medical health services. Therefore, a growing number of monitoring tasks is shifted to the public health administration at national stage, which – contrary to its original political intent – gains steadily on regulatory power. In my paper, I will discuss a recent dispute between the Zurich Seminar of Psychoanalysis (PSZ) and the national health administration over public recognition of the offered professional training services. I want to show how the national public health administration starts legally framing distinct forms of psychotherapy without even considering its further heuristic implications on successfully rendered mental health therapies. Rather, the national economic interests at stake, its legally labelled management techniques and its integration into epistemic communities such as the WHO or scientific networks of statistics remain the guiding stars of the day.

Navigating the Legal Pluralism in Refugee Camps: Customs, Culture and the National Law

Dr. Setu Gupta, Amity Institute of Advanced Legal Studies, Amity University, Noida, Uttar Pradesh, India, setugupta@hotmail.com

Legal pluralism in refugee camps in host countries manifests as a complex interplay between formal legal systems, informal norms, and hybrid legal mechanisms. This phenomenon is driven by the intersection of international, national, and customary laws within the unique socio-political landscape of refugee settlements. Refugees bring their own legal traditions and customary practices, which influence dispute resolution and community governance within camps. However, the host country's domestic legal framework also plays a significant role in shaping the rights and obligations of refugees. Based on secondary ethnographic research, the paper argues that informal norms of the refugees can lead to both, synergies and conflicts. These informal legal systems are critical for maintaining social order and addressing issues that formal mechanisms might overlook or inadequately handle. However, uninformed by the host country's normative order, such informal norms can lead to friction between the refugees and the host community. Hybrid legal mechanisms often emerge as a pragmatic response to this pluralism, blending elements of formal and informal systems to better cater to the specific needs of the refugee population. These mechanisms may include alternative dispute resolution methods, community-based justice initiatives, and collaborative governance structures involving refugees, host state authorities, and international agencies. The paper concludes that the actual transformative power of legal pluralism observed in refugee camps, lies in the such hybrid legal mechanisms which should be encouraged by the host countries for the benefit of all the stakeholders rather than making a hegemonic imposition of national law.

Reimagining Constitutional Law through a Folk Lens: How Folk Religious Traditions Inform Indonesia's Hukum Tata Negara

Pranoto Iskandar, McGill Centre for Human Rights & Legal Pluralism, pranoto.iskandar2@mail.mcgill.ca

In this presentation, I aim to show that the Indonesian conception of constitutional law, vernacularly known as *hukum tata negara*, should be understood as a folk religious category. To build this claim, I employ a “conceptual analysis” in order to reveal *hukum tata negara*'s embedded relative difference. By employing a conceptual analysis, it is arguable that comprehending “constitutional law” necessitates an examination of its usage in all typical contexts, encompassing legal and non-legal domains. This broad

approach is important, considering that the use of legal concepts in non-legal or ordinary domain may not be arbitrary. By positing that the Indonesian conception of constitutional law is rooted in ordinary language, it is necessary to prioritize local or indigenously produced sources over foreign and comparative sources. Nonetheless, this differentiation does not imply that foreign and comparative sources are unimportant. The rationale behind this differentiation strategy is to clarify the uniqueness while also establishing a connection between Indonesian and Western constitutionalism as a fusion between two constitutional traditions that are not necessarily incommensurable. As such, this presentation is intended to leverage local knowledge in shedding light on shared meanings and their significance in shaping Indonesia's modern legal landscape.

Grounding away from Home: Customary Law, Land Conflicts, and Migration in Southern Cameroon

Rosine Tchatchoua Djomo, Wageningen University & Research / Africa Studies Centre Leiden, tdrosine@gmail.com

This article examines land tenure changes and land conflicts in the context of rural migration in southern Cameroon. Drawing on qualitative research conducted in 2019, it focuses on how resolving land disputes plays a role in authority claims in the relationships between various migrant groups and host communities. The article demonstrates how the arrival of migrants over time has significantly changed the ethnic composition and social fabric of host communities, leading to changes in property relations and the support networks of public authorities. Ethnic groups that assert priority and native origin are no longer the predominant groups in the region. They are significantly outnumbered by migrant groups, who have introduced new traditions, land use practices, social structure, and governing systems. Perceptions of a dual land tenure regime – the communal land tenure in native villages versus the so-called ‘no man’s land’ outside native villages – have fueled the development of vernacular land markets. These perceptions have further shaped new tenurial arrangements and land rights in native and migrant territories. This article contributes to the existing literature by adding to our understanding of how displaced people reproduce customary practices and norms in a different traditional setting. It also highlights the implications of these findings for local governance and decentralization in southern Cameroon. It further provides valuable insights into resettlement challenges in other SSA settings where (forced) migration is ongoing and where statutory systems and different customary norms apply.

Living Customary law, the normative force of burial society contracts in Cape Town

Sinikiwe Mzezewa, Faculty of Law, Varsity College Cape Town, South Africa, smzezewa@varsitycollege.co.za

Funerals represent a cornerstone of cultural identity within black communities in South Africa and across the continent, encompassing rituals like weeklong vigils, specific attire for the bereaved, and ample provisions for mourners. To address the financial strain associated with these ceremonies, burial societies were formed in townships where unemployment and limited incomes are prevalent. Members pool both financial and non-financial resources, offering support in the event of a death in the family. This assistance includes financial aid and practical tasks such as meal preparation and burial arrangements. Beyond financial support, burial societies serve to strengthen social bonds and preserve cultural practices surrounding funerals. Governed by multi-party contracts, these societies operate with flexibility to accommodate the changing circumstances of their members. Contracts are established among individuals with pre-existing relationships, minimizing risks through the cultural currency of reputation. Emphasizing dignity, duties, and rights in line with customary practices, these contracts reflect the values of the community. Dispute resolution within burial societies prioritizes reconciliation and restoration of

relationships, drawing from customary law traditions rather than punitive measures. This paper, originating from my doctoral research, seeks to explore how living customary law operates within the framework of burial societies in Cape Town. By delving into this context, it aims to offer understanding on how and why living customary law functions alongside other norms, such as formal laws and self-made norms, in contemporary society.

Panel 3

The Transformative Power of Legal Pluralism in the Urban Realm (?)

Convenors: Danielle Chevalier, d.a.m.chevalier@law.leidenuniv.nl and Vera Setijawati, v.w.setijawati@law.leidenuniv.nl, Van Vollenhoven Institute for Law, Governance and Society, Leiden University

The UN estimates that since 2007 more than half of the world population lives in urban areas. Urbanization rates vary from 81% in high-income countries to 34% in low-income countries and are increasing across the globe (<https://ourworldindata.org/urbanization>). As UN Habitat formulates it: the future is urban (World Cities Report 2022 (unhabitat.org)). Cities and city life host a myriad of ideas, norms, rules and directives, and are governed by a plurality of normative orders, both statist and non-statist. State legal orders range vertically from the local to regional to national to supra-national, and horizontally from family law to administrative law to corporate law and beyond. Non-state orders include customary law, religious law and other normative registers organizing social life. Land issues, life events, commercial enterprises and so forth are all in play in an urban realm densely populated by diverse people, and the plurality of normative orders convenes and conflicts in the state-market-citizen triangle of the urban (Carolien Jacobs, Danielle Chevalier & Michiel Stapper (2024) Legal pluralism in the urban realm: an introduction, *Legal Pluralism and Critical Social Analysis*, DOI: 10.1080/27706869.2024.2320000). This panel invites contributions that take a legal pluralism lens to urban dynamics. The panel follows the theme of the conference and inquires after the transformative power of legal pluralism for the urban future, in the quest for a just city. The focus lies specifically with how the existence of multiple regulatory frames offer both challenges to and opportunities for the people carving out a life in the urban realm.

Legal Pluralism in Society as the Basis for Indonesian Legal Development

Retno Kus Setyowati, Faculty of Law, Universitas Krisnadwipayana, Jakarta, Indonesia, retno@unkris.ac.id

Legal pluralism is defined as legal diversity, which occurs as a result of centralization and positivism in the application of law in society, especially those that regulate social relations. Thus, legal pluralism thrives in urban communities, whose residents have a variety of backgrounds due to differences in ethnicity, religion and belief, as well as cultural diversity. Urbanization is a reflection of differences in growth and uneven development facilities between one region and another, between rural areas and urban areas that encourage population movement. The results of the analysis in the paper show that the social problems caused by urbanization are very complex. The rapid and sudden increase in urban population, unemployment, the growth of slums and homelessness, increasing crime, traffic congestion, business competition, are all social impacts of urbanization in big cities. Negative impacts like this require regulations that can accommodate and solve problems that may arise in social relations in society. Legal development at the same time can also be interpreted as legal reform. Efforts to reform and develop the law have at least three important things that require attention, namely: (1) the law itself, (2) the law enforcement apparatus, and (3) legal awareness of the community as a whole. These three aspects are interrelated, so that if one of the three things does not function properly, then legal life in society will not function properly either.

The City, the Law and the Skateboarder's Scene: Municipal regulatory interventions in an anti-authoritarian normative order

Dr. Danielle Chevalier, Assistant Professor Law & Society, Van Vollenhoven Institute for Law, Governance and Society, Leiden Law School, d.a.m.chevalier@law.leidenuniv.nl

Urban space is produced by the social life that resides in it, but it is also an incubator for new social entities. Skateboarders are an example in case. The built environment and socio-economic constellation of the Californian seaside slum 'Dogtown', and the prolonged environmental drought of the 1970s, famously combined into a specific set of circumstances that paved the way for the subculture of skateboarding. Skateboarding came about as a counter-culture, a social entity with its own norms and rules, an 'outlaw' scene running counter to the etiquette of mainstream society. From these origins grew a global phenomenon: nowadays an estimated 50 million riders skateboard worldwide. Since 2020 it is a recognized Olympic sport. As skateboarding grew in popularity, authorities have struggled on how to deal with it. Norway notably enacted a nationwide ban (from 1978 to 1989), but on the whole regulation is attempted at the municipal level. Often with limited success. Bordeaux, France was one of the first cities to flip policy; instead of trying to ban the activity, local authorities tried to connect with skateboarders to regulate them. Many other cities followed suit, seeking collaboration with their skateboarding communities not just to regulate but also to accommodate. And not just to accommodate, but also to market their cities as 'most-skateboarding friendly' (city slogan of Malmö, Sweden). Using the city of Amsterdam as a case study, this paper unpacks how authorities tap into the normative frames and cultural repertoire of the skateboarder community for regulation and governance purposes, and how this in turn impacts the normative autonomy and cultural singularity of the skateboarding scene.

Urban Spatial Legal Pluralism and its Societal Impacts in Jakarta: Space, Land, Water, and River

Vera W. Setijawati Soemarwi, Van Vollenhoven Institute for Law, Governance and Society, Leiden University, v.w.setijawati@law.leidenuniv.nl

Many scholars have criticized urban spatial legal pluralism in Indonesia, notably on how the authorities distribute space and allocate the city's resources and how this impacts poor city-dwellers. Building on this literature this paper discusses the political economy of distributing space, land, water, and river in Jakarta Province, looking in particular at the so-called 'river normalization'. Who are the major actors in this process? What is the impact of 'river normalization' on the marginalized Jakartans who live in self-arrangement kampongs, like Kampung Pulo? As our point of departure, we take the presence of urban spatial legal pluralism, which enables the provincial authority to arbitrarily expropriate kampung dweller's land. Their legal mandate gives them the power to select which urban spatial regulation can be applied to support their sustainable development agenda, which mainly serves the interests of private business and developers. In the paper we consider how under conditions of spatial legal pluralism "political authority produces rights, and vice-versa" (Lund and Rahman 2018, Suhardiman et al 2021).

The Spatio-legality of Street Tout Practices in Urban Hong Kong

Dr. Dhiraj Nainani, Postdoctoral Fellow at the Asia Research Institute, National University of Singapore, DHIRAJN@nus.edu.sg

In studying Chungking Mansions, a building complex located in Hong Kong, I build upon Chevalier and Stapper's (2024) recent intervention to explore how the built environment and urban space *influences* and is *influenced* by legal regulation and surveillance. Here, thousands belonging to Hong Kong's minority South Asian population live and work (at times informally or illegally) in a place dubbed the city's 'last ghetto', which stands in contrast to its affluent, sanitised, and hyper-modern surroundings. Using an

approach that combines critical geography scholarship and ethnographic fieldwork, I trace Chungking Mansions through the contestations of power that inevitably arise between the regulation of ‘local’ space and the ‘others’ that inhabit it. I specifically focus on how the street touts that work right outside Chungking Mansions illustrate the interpolation of law, space, and power in four ways: a) the *reorganisation* of street space from movement to commerce; b) the *reiteration* of intra-Asian identities when forming tout communities; c) the *resistance* against police surveillance; and d) the *reproduction* of surveillance with regards to the male gaze. Studying Chungking Mansions in this way allows for a distinctly subaltern or ‘Other’ intervention within spatio-legal understandings of the Asian urban, which itself has tended to be subsumed by an overwhelming focus on Anglo-Centric space and normativity. At the same time, framing the building complex as a distinctly spatial *and* legal assemblage reveals not only how it is enmeshed within Hong Kong’s broader urban fabric, but how it remains a vital site of alternative globalisation as well.

Weaving Places: Legal plurality, urbanization and Indigenous sovereignty in the Pacific

Rebecca Monson, ANU College of Law, The Australian National University, rebecca.monson@anu.edu.au

In June 2024, the Solomon Islands National University held an international conference on its campus in the national capital, Honiara. At the conference opening, speakers and other guests were led into the auditorium by a group of young women stamping and singing, and then welcomed on to the traditional lands of the Tadaï people by representatives of their House of Chiefs. This traditional welcome acknowledged and reinforced the authority of the Tadaï people as the traditional custodians of the lands, and it was the first time any such welcome had occurred at an international conference in Solomon Islands. This paper asks where Indigenous sovereignty figures in the process of transforming space from ‘customary’ into ‘urban’ in ‘post-colonial’, Indigenous-majority, Solomon Islands. I draw on threads of Pacific Studies, legal pluralism, and legal geography scholarship to suggest that Pacific urban areas should be understood as ‘weaving places’ – places in which new legal pluralities are woven, as well as places woven out of many threads of law by many social actors. This intense legal plurality is not simply a ‘by product’ of urban life but a defining feature of it; it is central to the production of space as urban. Yet as the official welcome by the Tadaï people reminded conference-goers, urbanization also entails material and discursive erasures of traditional custodians, landscapes and legal regimes, and the production of truly ‘post-colonial’ space requires disruption of these erasures.

The Role of Legal Pluralism in Sustainable Development of Indonesia's New Capital City

Diani Sadiawati, Edward Benedictus Roring, Faculty Law, Universitas Pembangunan Nasional “Veteran” Jakarta, dianisadiawati@upnvj.ac.id, edwardbenedictus22@gmail.com

The planning and development of Indonesia's new capital, Nusantara, faces various legal, social and environmental challenges. One important approach in dealing with this challenge is legal pluralism, which recognizes the existence of various legal systems that coexist, including state law, customary law and religious law. This article discusses the role of legal pluralism in supporting sustainable development in the archipelago. Legal pluralism allows the integration of sustainability principles by taking into account local wisdom and the values of local communities. This research shows that recognition and respect for customary laws and traditional practices can increase community participation, maintain biodiversity, and reduce social conflict. Thus, legal pluralism contributes to achieving sustainable development goals, including poverty reduction, sustainable management of natural resources, and improving the quality of life of the population. This study emphasizes the importance of an inclusive and adaptive legal framework to achieve the long-term vision of a sustainable and globally competitive new capital city.

Formulating Inheritance of the Family Home: Legal Pluralism and Caring Relationships in Urban Indonesia

Santy Kouwagam, Van Vollenhoven Institute for Law, Governance and Development, Leiden University, s.u.kouwagam@law.leidenuniv.nl & Vania Erlangga, Stichting Socio-Legal Consulting, vaniaerlangaa@gmail.com

This paper investigates the complexities surrounding inheritance rights to the family home in urban Indonesia, emphasizing the intersection of legal pluralism and caring relationships. It examines how diverse legal, societal, cultural, and religious norms influence entitlement to the family home, particularly through the lens of support for the elderly. By scrutinizing these frameworks, including both financial and non-monetary forms of assistance, the study underscores their implications for social equity and justice within the urban landscape.

Panel 4

Legal temporalities and pluralism from the perspective of people's experiences of law

Convenors: Kwamou Eva Feukeu, Max Planck Institute for Comparative and International Private Law, Hamburg, feukeu@mpipriv.de, Anthony Diala University of the Western Cape, South Africa, adiala@uwc.ac.za

Abstract: Law and temporality are closely linked. Often, whoever influences the direction and meaning of time in legal issues dictates power dynamics. Recent problematisation of time by sociolegal scholars (e.g. Mawani 2014) has expanded the prescriptions and limitations of procedural law. Contemporary discussions in Europe focus on juridical time and time as a delineator of rights. In the global South, however, scholars have documented more than one archive of 'time' in law (Bidima 2004). State law, especially in the era of globalisation, occupies a timespace different from transnational agendas (Santos 2020). Here, time in law has multidimensionality because normative orders and scales of law are multiple. What the debate misses is a connection with those who experience law on the ground (Feukeu 2024). This Panel probes the relationships of legal users with time. How do legal users mobilise time? How do their relationships shape law's evolution? What are the temporalities of customary and religious laws? How does time help us understand the interaction of normative orders? We argue that sensitivity to the interplay of time and law illumines how legal pluralism, especially in its adaptive sense (Diala 2017, 2021), contributes to legal theory.

Sustaining tradition, the archives of customary and state law that live within us

Kwamou Eva Feukeu, Max Planck Institute for Comparative and International Private Law, Hamburg, feukeu@mpipriv.de

Abstract missing

Plurilegality and the Cautious Pursuit of Marriage in Contemporary South Africa

Michael Yarbrough, Dept of Political Science, John Jay College of Criminal Justice; Doctoral Faculty, Department of Sociology, CUNY Graduate Center, michaelyarbrough.net, myarbrough@jjay.cuny.edu

In many black South African communities, marriage often combines two processes grounded in different legalities that enact two different relationships to time. One process, known in Nguni languages

as *ukulobola* or simply *lobola*, entails a negotiated series of payments and ceremonies between the families of the two spouses, typically centered on a large gift of literal or metaphorical cattle from the groom to the bride's family. Lobola is ideally ongoing and open-ended, and the status of the marriage can be ambiguous and contested. The other process is the "white wedding" performed in a Christian or state context, in which an outside authority confers the status of "married" onto the couple "until death us do part." Drawing on ethnographic research among both heterosexual and LGBTQ+ informants, I argue that many use the different temporalities of these processes to manage their desires and anxieties around marriage. On the one hand, many of my interlocutors deeply hope to achieve the stable status of marriage in order to "build a family" and "move forward in life." On the other hand, many also fear the risks of binding themselves indefinitely to a spouse or spousal family who may prove undesirable. Some of my interlocutors thus use the open-ended process of lobola as a way to manage these anxieties, "studying" or "watching" their intended spouse while lobola continues before deciding whether they want to secure the relationship's status with a formal wedding.

Via Side Routes: Informal Cross-Border Activities in the Daily Life of Border Communities on Sebatik Island, Indonesia

Muhammad Ad'har Nasir, independent researcher, muhammadadharnasir@gmail.com

Kalibrasi (Kajian Lintas-Batas dan Migrasi) Sebatik Island, North Kalimantan, is one of the regions of Indonesia that directly borders Sabah, Malaysia. The cross-border interaction of people and commodities between the two countries through informal routes, or as the people of Sebatik Island call it, via side routes, has become the customary law. Even though it is contrary to state law, this practice still occurs due to economic and social needs, geographical proximity, and more efficient travel times than formal routes. Borders in many countries play a role in separating and connecting, in which conflict and negotiation occur between society and the state. This research examines the interaction of state law and customary law in cross-border activities through informal routes based on community experiences. Then, it identifies which individuals from certain social groups find it easy and difficult to cross state borders through informal routes. Using ethnographic research methods on Sebatik Island, this research finds that customary law is semi-autonomous. The state intervenes with several requirements for individuals from certain social groups can cross state borders through informal routes. However, there are individuals from social groups who find it difficult to cross but get around this through other informal routes. This research also found that it is relatively easy for social groups to cross national borders through informal routes, usually for trading necessities and familial relationships. Meanwhile, undocumented migrant workers are one of the social groups who find it difficult to cross informally but get around this through other informal routes.

Temporality and the Foundational Values of African Customary Law

Anthony Diala, University of the Western Cape, South Africa, adiala@uwc.ac.za

Temporality is significant in law because the direction of time in legal issues influences power dynamics. Given that customary law is widely acknowledged as a flexible normative system, it offers a useful lens for analysing temporality. While the flexibility of customary law assists judges to determine current practices, it makes the ascertainment of customary laws difficult for ethnographers, since people's practices change in response to the socioeconomic realities of globalisation. Based on fieldwork in South Africa, I argue that the foundational values of customary law mitigate its flexibility problem because they are more stable than the practices they inspire. For example, although bridewealth has changed forms, its payment persists because it socially legitimates marriage and recognises the bride's fecundity. Similarly, laws of inheritance allocate the family house to the eldest male child (primogeniture) or the youngest male

child (ultimogeniture) because of their foundational value of preserving the ancestral home. I fill the gap in the debate on temporality by illuminating the lived experiences of those who observe customary law in intersectional social fields.

Temporalities and the pluralistic approach to decolonial property law

Harison Citrawan, National Research and Innovation Agency (BRIN), harison.citrawan@brin.go.id

This paper examines the relationship between legal temporalities and decoloniality through an investigation of how the mobilization of trauma of dispossession shapes the ways post-colonial legal decision-makers develop a pluralistic approach to property law. In doing so, it identifies the aesthetic dimension of property law informed by linguistic elements applied by the legal decision-makers (i.e., judges) in creating lawful relations in relevant legal cases. Building on the methodological underpinnings in decolonial comparative law, it is claimed that decolonizing property law is essentially construed upon the images of spatiotemporal configuration of post-colonial lived experience. By taking Indonesia's jurisprudential reasoning on water remunicipalization and Adat forest recognition as a case-study, these spatiotemporal images are shaped by what Bakhtin's literary vision calls hybridization (of property)—that is, a synthesis of space and time in the narratives that shape judges' reasoning in assigning meaning to legal relations. The hybridization of property can be found in the judges' enactment of legal principles in the two cases, spanning from the concepts of ownership, freedom of contract, causality of harm, to the universality of rights. Ultimately, this study suggests that decolonizing property law must demonstrate overlapping temporal affective dialogues between, on the one hand, the trauma of past colonial extractivism, and, on the other hand, the anticipated future trajectories of resource governance.

Panel 5

Flowing Beyond Borders: Exploring Legal Pluralism in Water Governance across Indonesia and Asia

Convenor: Widya Tuslian, Van Vollenhoven Institute for Law, Governance and Development, Leiden University, w.n.tuslian@law.leidenuniv.nl

Water governance, akin to the fluidity of water itself, operates within dynamic and multifaceted contexts, impacting diverse societies and sectors. This complexity necessitates the intersection of various legal frameworks, leading to what is termed legal pluralism. In Indonesia, shaped by its rich cultural heritage and colonial history, legal pluralism deeply influences water administration. This panel seeks to delve into Indonesia's intricate water governance system, examining the legacy of colonialism and its ongoing influence on modern policies. Furthermore, extending beyond Indonesia, the panel aims to explore legal pluralism in water governance across wider Asia. The region's diverse cultures, traditions, and legal systems present unique challenges and opportunities for effective water resource management. Through case studies from transboundary river basins like the Mekong, Indus, and Ganga-Brahmaputra-Meghna, the panel will highlight the complexities of navigating legal pluralism in managing shared water resources. By examining the intersections between formal statutory law and customary practices, the panel will shed light on the nuances of legal pluralism in water governance. It will address challenges such as reconciling differing legal interpretations, negotiating water rights, and promoting cooperation among multiple stakeholders. Ultimately, the panel aims to foster a deeper understanding of legal pluralism's role in shaping water governance practices across Indonesia and Asia. Through insightful analysis and robust discussion, it seeks to identify pathways toward equitable and sustainable solutions for managing shared water resources in the region.

Unsettled Rivers: Customary Fishing Rights in Colonial Bengal

Shalini Iyengar, PhD Candidate, Department of Anthropology, Yale University, shalini.iyengar@yale.edu

Sometime in the late 19th century, a section of the river Ganga broke through the land of a zamindar in East Bengal and although small, this new channel was still substantial enough for small boats to navigate its waters. The landowner appears to have been alive to the potential fishing such waterway allowed but unfortunately, he was not to be allowed to fish in peace. Instead, a downstream proprietor of fishing rights filed a case against him, alleging that the latter had committed trespass since the stream joined the waters over which the former exercised his rights. The case hinged on the question of custom – did the customary right of fishery follow the river, no matter its course? Cases such as the above would come to be common in the Bengal delta. At the heart of these matters was the question of customary rights over-fishing, rights which had evolved over millennia of close correspondence with a fluid landscape which challenged fixities of ownership. In this paper, I trace the judicial understanding of customary law in the series of cases filed over customary rights over-fishing in Bengal between the mid-19th and early 20th centuries. I use the legal record to trace the changing understandings of customs between the colonial state and its subjects and in order to examine how these changes reflected tensions between multiple legal orders – a British legal system conditioned by the primacy of the Magna Carta, a colonial legal system driven by the imperatives of revenue maximization, and a customary legal order shaped by both historical legacies and then-present realities. By itself, a case can be little more than a record of a dispute, a replacement for conflict by another means but when seen in context, a case reveals itself as a site where multiple competing interests are contested and negotiated. In this paper, I explore the fishing rights cases in colonial Bengal to examine colonial legal anxieties over control, boundaries, and stability; an anxiety which the complex political ecology of the region did little to assuage and a great deal to exacerbate.

Forms of Protection of Local Wisdom in Water Resources Management in Indonesia

Nadia Astriani, Faculty of Law, Universitas Padjadjaran, nadia.astriani@unpad.ac.id

Water has always been the center of human life. Therefore, every settlement has always been built near water resources. Awareness of the importance of water for life has given rise to local wisdom in managing and protecting water resources. Local wisdom practiced in a downward trend has maintained multiple water resources in Indonesia. As society is increasingly capitalistic and individualistic, local wisdom is eroded. However, in some areas, it is still maintained. One of the efforts to sustain this local wisdom is by adopting it in regional regulations. This effort is certainly not easy; some parties think that institutionalizing local wisdom in regional regulations erodes the essence of local wisdom itself, so instead of adopting it, it is better to protect water resources within regulations. This article explains more about efforts to protect local wisdom in water resources management in Indonesia.

Indigenous People's Agency in Legal Pluralism of Transboundary River Governance: A Case Study of the Hulu Sembakung River, North Borneo

Puji Hastuti, Research Center for Population, National Research and Innovation Agency, pujisht@gmail.com, Afdil Hafidh, independent researcher, afdil.hafid@gmail.com

The Sembakung River Basin illustrates the complexities of legal pluralism in post-colonial transboundary river governance in Asia. Colonialism partitioned indigenous communities between Indonesia and Malaysia, yet those in Lumbis, North Kalimantan, Indonesia, and Pensiangan, Sabah, Malaysia, maintain unity through traditional jar exchange rituals. Despite state border surveillance, Indigenous actors negotiate state regulations. This paper adopts Schendel & Abraham's "illicitness" perspective, suggesting state-local consensus can legitimize perceived illegal commodities. It delves into historical and

contemporary water management in the basin, emphasizing colonial legacies and the impact of cross-border rituals on water policies. Ethnographic methods provide insights into indigenous experiences, with the author engaging directly through observation and interviews. The findings underscore the Indigenous communities' agency in Hulu Sembakung to negotiate state power, depicting them as adept agents shaping their destiny and norms. The jar exchange ritual symbolizes their unity and regulates cross-border social interactions. Local agency significantly influences transboundary river governance. This research examines how legal pluralism impacts cross-border water governance, particularly in the Sembakung River Basin, providing insights into broader dynamics in Indonesia-Malaysia and Asia. It informs policy discussions and advocates for fair and sustainable solutions in managing shared water resources, emphasizing the importance of integrating local indigenous agencies and legal pluralism for success.

Power and Pluralism: The Interplay of Law and Informal Governance in Urban Water Projects

Widya Tuslian, Van Vollenhoven Institute for Law, Governance and Development, Leiden University, The Netherlands, w.n.tuslian@law.leidenuniv.nl

This presentation delves into the intricate dynamics of legal pluralism in Jakarta by examining a water pipe construction project in urban poor settlements. The research highlights the multifaceted interactions between various stakeholders, including local residents, master meter owners, and civil society organizations, and their influence on the project's trajectory. Through detailed fieldwork, this study tries to uncover the ways in which formal legal frameworks and informal governance structures intersect and often clash, creating a complex environment for infrastructure development. The study identifies several critical moments of conflict and negotiation, such as the disruptions and the involvement of politically connected civil society groups. These incidents underscore the challenges of implementing infrastructure projects in settings where multiple legal and informal systems coexist. The presentation will discuss how local customs, power dynamics, and political affiliations can either facilitate or hinder project progress, offering a nuanced understanding of legal pluralism in action. By analyzing these interactions, this study provides insights into the strategies employed by different stakeholders to assert their interests and the implications for broader governance and policy-making. The findings reveal the necessity for adaptive and context-sensitive approaches to infrastructure development in legally pluralistic environments. Key recommendations will be presented to improve the management and implementation of such projects, emphasizing the importance of inclusive and participatory planning processes that acknowledge and navigate the diverse legal landscapes. This study contributes to the broader discourse on legal pluralism and urban governance, providing valuable lessons for similar contexts across Indonesia and Asia.

Panel 6

Recognition of customary justice systems – a double-edged sword

Convenors: Janine Ubink, Van Vollenhoven Institute for Law, Governance and development, Leiden University, j.m.ubink@law.leidenuniv.nl, Rebecca Monson, Australia National University, rebecca.monson@anu.edu.au

The recognition of customary or indigenous justice systems and traditional authority structures can symbolize an equal relationship with state institutions and enhance protection of indigenous/customary communities and their rights to and authority over land in their territory. State recognition of non-state normative orderings, however, never entails a wholesale acceptance of these systems without conditions or exceptions. It is usually partial, conditional, and meant to make the customary order governable, subordinate, and in line with normative values of the state. Processes of recognition are thus intricately connected with questions of political power and sovereignty, control and subjugation, integration and exclusion. A role for the state in the recognition of customary law and (the

determination of) indigenous / traditional leaders can also be an important part of the production of the state as a legitimate authority. Decisions around the governance of legal pluralism are seldom based on ‘a conversation among equals’ (Gargarella 2022), but mostly result from a situation where state authorities, laws, and courts determine the breadth, scope, and validity of customary law and indigenous claims to authority. The neutral term recognition – which seems to imply wholesale acceptance of existing norms and structures – masks state limitations, intervention, regulation, and reform, and will inevitably entail a reordering and transformation of authority and power. National and international law increasingly provide protection to indigenous groups. However, to benefit from such protection requires indigenous groups to fulfill criteria established by ‘the other’, usually the post-colonial or settler state or the international community, and to accept a position within a larger nation state rather than continue their fight for sovereignty and full authority over their land in accordance with their own legal and administrative structures. Often, to be recognized as an indigenous community requires proof of a continued traditional way of life, leading to unhelpful results where indigenous groups who are trying to reclaim lands that have been appropriated by invading settlers or the (colonial / post-colonial) state do not qualify as indigenous group because they don’t have any lands they still administer and use in the traditional way. In other cases, indigenous groups are granted access to natural resources but only for traditional forms of economic activity such as hunting or fishing with traditional methods and gear. This ‘jamming into categories’ of indigenous groups is also connected to regional differences and the global movement of international law norms and concepts. Recognition – of indigenous communities, of local leaders – also brings up questions of representation. Studies point to the complexity of identifying who comprise the community and who can legitimately represent it. Particularly when community representation is connected to decision-making regarding valuable resources (land, extractive resources) leadership and representation are hotly contested. Who can take decisions on behalf of these communities, who do outside actors (governmental agencies, judges, companies) accept or designate as such? And how does leadership recognition impact elite formation and existing social hierarchies? Which people and groups get included and excluded in the process? In this panel, we bring together stories on trajectories of and struggles around recognition and underlying questions of community identification and representation. We’d like to bring out possible advantages and positive stories around recognition, as well as the ‘violence’ (after Watson 2012) of state recognition, the jamming into categories and state supremacy claims that indigenous people are confronted with to qualify for certain protections and levels of autonomy, and alternative claims and strategies of indigenous groups to protect their authority and lands.

Hybrid Legal Orders: Exploring the Advantages and Risks of Integrating Fast-Track Customary Justice into Contemporary Justice

Dr Lisa Denney, Principal Research Fellow and Deputy Director, Centre for Human Security and Social Change, La Trobe University Centre for Social Impact, L.Denney@latrobe.edu.au

Renée Chartres, Senior Land and Legal Advisor, Land Equity International, RChartres@landequity.com.au

There is a growing recognition of legal pluralism and the centrality of hybrid legal orders to people’s lived experience of disputes and grievances amongst academics, governments and the international justice community. Increasingly, this is leading to calls for greater engagement, integration or coordination of formal state legal systems and those systems beyond the state. Yet these calls – and the action that follows – also risks significant harm to non-state justice systems, which are invariably incorporated into a hierarchy in which they are at the bottom and their laws are curtailed by those of the state. This paper seeks to examine practical examples of more productive modes of engagement across legal orders, drawing on diverse contexts in sub-Saharan Africa and the Pacific. The paper takes seriously the empirical reality of legal pluralism and thus the need for governments and the international justice community to engage with it in efforts to improve access to and delivery of justice – but is mindful of the many pitfalls and challenges along the way. The paper will examine the use of hybrid customary systems

to resolve land disputes in the context of land regularization programs, and how to introduce models that allow for scale up whilst retaining the integrity and flexibility in locally devised dispute processes.

Judicial Marginalization of Communal Land Tenure in South Africa: A Critique of CASAC

Dr. Thomas Coggin, Senior Lecturer, University of the Witwatersrand, thomas.coggin@wits.ac.za

The South African CASAC case concerned a tenure dispute between customary law communities and the Ingonyama Trust, over land straddling an urban-rural divide in the province of Kwazulu-Natal. The Trust, which holds the land for the benefit and welfare of its communities, attempted to convert customary land tenure into common law leaseholds, positioning itself as the owner and the residents as tenants. The residents argued this ignored their customary law ownership rights, indicated partly through apartheid-era Permission to Occupy (PTO) certificates. These certificates, initially representing less-than-ownership rights, have gained new significance through customary law practice, and are now a symbol of customary ownership rights. The CASAC court recognized this symbolism in its outcome but, in its reasoning, it struggled to position customary law within a broader South African legal context. In this paper, I evaluate the court's reasoning, and I illustrate how South African law can better accommodate the legal plurality inherent in the residents' claims to the land. I argue there was room to affirm customary law tenure on its own accord, and I problematize how CASAC constrains the development of customary law by relying on other South African legal sources to define and validate customary land rights. This approach avoids the plurality of legal sources underpinning the customary law claim, ultimately marginalizing customary land law. The case also demonstrates the difficulties courts face in incorporating 'diverse interpretations of how relations to land are constituted', which may 'vary, complement, overlap, or even come into conflict with one another...' (Griffiths, 2019: 7).

Land corruption, the law and struggles over mining revenues in rural South Africa

Sonwabile Mnwana, Department of Sociology at Rhodes University, South Africa, sonwabile.mnwana@ru.ac.za

The paper contributes to the burgeoning literature on land corruption in Africa. Drawing on the case of the struggles over platinum-rich land and mining royalties in rural South Africa, the paper interrogates the ambivalent role of law in the context of prolonged conflict. Traditional leaders (chiefs), with the tacit support of state officials and bolstered by controversial legislation pieces, have positioned themselves as custodians of land and mining royalties in the former Bantustan areas, where access to land is defined through customary systems of tenure. This has led significant resistance by local residents, who have been defined as 'traditional communities' by the law. Conflict is characterized by exclusive group claims over land, corruption allegations against local chiefs and episodes of violent protests targeting mining operations. Quite often, these struggles end up in the courts of law and commissions of inquiry. I argue that, in the context of prolonged conflict, the law itself is a field of power and its role can be better understood as part of the political economy of corruption in post-apartheid South Africa. Therefore, the role of legislation and the courts is contested. Moreover, these rural struggles demonstrate that land corruption is an aspect of the broader political economy and politics of corruption, and cannot be adequately understood if it is perceived or analysed solely as an element of crime or a moral challenge in African societies (Von Holdt 2019).

The Limits of Traditional Authority: A Case for Balancing Representative and Participatory Democracy in Rural Governance

Wandile Brian Zondo, PhD Candidate in Public Law at the University of Cape Town, wandilezondo3@gmail.com

This paper explores the dynamics of rural governance in South Africa, highlighting the tension between traditional leadership and participatory democracy. It argues that the increasing dominance of traditional authorities in rural governance has narrowed the democratic processes, neglecting the normative objectives of public participation and customary law. The paper contends that this approach is unconstitutional and challenges the notion that traditional leaders have unilateral decision-making authority over land, governance, and natural resources. The paper examines the historical and constitutional backdrop of traditional authorities in South Africa, exploring their roles, significance, and impact on rural governance. It also analyses foundational cases that offer profound insights into public participation in land administration, traditional governance structures, and exploiting natural resources crucial to customary life and livelihood. The paper challenges the assumption that traditional leaders are sufficient proxies for public participation, arguing that this approach is inadequate and susceptible to manipulation. Instead, it advocates for a broader understanding of customary law that acknowledges its dimensions conducive to participatory democracy. The paper recommends a policy that harmonizes traditional authority with the principles of participatory democracy, promoting inclusive and effective rural governance. The paper concludes that the power dynamics between traditional authorities and rural communities create an unconstitutional hierarchy favouring representative over participatory democracy. However, both forms of democracy are indispensable and mutually reinforcing in a constitutional democracy. The paper recommends a more inclusive and effective rural governance system incorporating customary law, promoting community development, improving service delivery, and nurturing social cohesion in rural settings.

The Traditional Courts Act of South Africa in isiZulu: Translation is not enough to facilitate access to justice and to decolonize law

Thiyane Duda, Land and Accountability Research Centre, University of Cape Town, Thiyane.duda@uct.ac.za

In 2023 the Traditional Courts Act (TCA) of 2022, which regulates access and administration of justice in rural South Africa, was enacted. The Act is published in English and isiZulu, two of the twelve official languages of South Africa. IsiZulu is one of nine official isiNtu (Southern African indigenous) languages in South Africa. National legislation is rarely published in isiNtu languages, as it is often only published in English and Afrikaans, the official languages of the colonial and apartheid regimes. This paper argues that although publishing legislation in isiNtu languages is a progressive and encouraged development towards facilitating access to justice, decolonizing law, and realising South Africa's plural legal system in the legislation; translation is insufficient to achieve this. The TCA attempt has many problems. The isiZulu text was only published after the Act was signed, meaning that there was no public consultation. Only the English text was assented to, therefore giving it precedence over the isiZulu text. IsiZulu is the most spoken language in South Africa while English is the fourth, and many people in rural areas do not speak English. The text is directly translated from English to isiZulu, and remains English in meaning and epistemology. The Act also introduces new and inconsistent concepts in isiZulu. This generates confusion and discord between the text and the lived reality. To realise the TCA's potential, consultation with isiZulu speakers who practice isiNtu law is key for the legislation to reflect the epistemologies and socio-cultural context that produces it.

Land and Labor: The Relations of Matrilineal Community and Capitalism in West Sumatra, Indonesia

Almonika Cindy Fatika Sari, Lecturer at Department of Customary Law, Faculty of Law, Universitas Gadjah Mada, almonika.cindy.f@ugm.ac.id

The autonomy of matrilineal Minangkabau farmers is rooted in a shared access system to communal land (ulayat kaum or harato pusako) and open forest reserves (ulayat nagari). Governed by a matrilineal socio-political structure, decisions are made through communal forums. This study aims to explore how traditional matrilineal social structures in West Sumatra interact with modern capitalist economies, particularly focusing on land tenure and labour patterns as fundamental modes of production in rural life. Fieldwork was conducted in Nagari Sungai Kamuyang, a matrilineal community on the slopes of Mount Sago in West Sumatra, where small-scale agriculture is the primary livelihood. The relationship between the Minangkabau people and their customary land is dynamic, evolving with social reproduction and the interplay of customary, Islamic, and state laws. The interaction between state and nonstate laws shapes land access and labour distribution. Capitalism influences legal negotiations in controlling customary land, highlighting the complex interplay between traditional practices and modern economic pressures.

Recognition or domestication of customary actors? Analysis of recent initiatives for access to justice in African contexts where legal pluralism is not organized by law: Burkina Faso, Burundi, DRC

Julien Moriceau, PhD student at Université Catholique de Louvain, Julien.moriceau@inanga.org, Julien2870@gmail.com

Burkina Faso, Burundi, DRC are characterized by a lack of recognition of the dispute resolution role of customary actors. However, as elsewhere in Africa, customary actors in rural settings are used as state's intermediaries and act as local administrative authorities (Ubink 2008, Tieleman & Uitermark 2019). In these contexts, pilot initiatives aimed at improving access to justice and involving customary actors are flourishing, de facto experimenting with ways of recognizing pluralism. This presentation, at the crossroads of legal anthropology and development studies, is based on semi-structured interviews with various actors (local, state, development, litigants) conducted in rural areas between 2015 and 2023. This paper argues that behind this objective of recognition and their so-called innovative or alternative feature, these initiatives led by development actors allow for little or no 'conversation among equals' (Gargarella 2022). Those initiatives may reproduce, behind an appearance of recognition, a top-down approach of 'domestication' of customary actors by the State, already used by the colonial power. Customary actors are only trusted with minor offenses and are systematically placed under the supervision of state justice actors. There is no reciprocity in the activities carried out: the aim is to bring customary justice closer to state justice, but never the opposite. Moreover, the temporality of these actions is transitory, as if to give litigants time to adopt state justice. Finally, the paper draws on the importance of setting up a conversation among equals by outlining the practical obstacles and the lack of consciousness of practitioners.

The Urgency of Legal Protection of the Rights of Indigenous Peoples in the Era of Disruption

Aprilia Stefany Leliak, S.H., M.H, (Doctor of Law Program, University of Gadjah Mada, Indonesia, apriastefanyleliak@mail.ugm.ac.id)

Indigenous peoples in Indonesia have traditions, norms, and legal systems that have been maintained for generations. The existence of unwritten customary law, in the form of values that exist in communities, still applies and is recognized by the Indonesian state. Such law plays an important role in the sustainability of the natural environment, the maintenance of social relations and distinctive customary values. As the Era of Disruption, globalization is a process that affects people's lives including the rapid rise of capitalism, so that globalization brings us a new order of life. In the face of these challenges, it is important to take adequate measures to strengthen and protect the existence of customary law. This

research uses a normative juridical legal approach to determine the development of customary law and the protection of indigenous peoples in the current era of disruption.

Navigating the Legal Landscape: Empowering Khoi-San Communities through Customary Law Recognition

Christa Rautenbach, North-West University, Potchefstroom Campus, South Africa,
Christa.Rautenbach@nwu.ac.za

In the wake of the Traditional and Khoi-San Leadership Act 3 of 2019, the journey towards formal recognition of Khoi-San communities in South Africa has encountered both promise and peril. This presentation delves into the transformative potential of legal pluralism by scrutinising the provisions of the Leadership Act and their implications for Khoi-San customary law, communities and leadership. Despite the Act's intended role as a blueprint for recognition and governance, its journey has been marred by legal setbacks, epitomised by the Constitutional Court's declaration of unconstitutionality in *Mogale v Speaker of the National Assembly* 2023 (6) SA 58 (CC). As the deadline for rectification looms (30 May 2025) it becomes imperative to dissect the Act's provisions, particularly its criteria for recognition, and to confront the challenges hindering the revival of Khoi-San traditions and leadership. Key areas of focus include the Act's definitions, its stipulations regarding historical lineage, customary practices, leadership structures, and cultural heritage, all against the backdrop of a rapidly evolving societal landscape. Central to the discourse is the question of whether the Act provides a viable path towards reclaiming what has been lost amidst centuries of assimilation. By shedding light on the ambiguities within the Act and the absence of interpretative guidelines, this presentation seeks to unravel the complexities inherent in the recognition process. It underscores the urgency of addressing these challenges within the two-year timeframe while advocating for a nuanced understanding of Khoi-San identity. Ultimately, this presentation serves as a call to action, urging stakeholders to navigate the intricate legal terrain with sensitivity and foresight. It underscores the pivotal role of enabling legislation in shaping the destiny of Khoi-San communities and emphasises the enduring nature of their struggle for recognition. Through an analysis of the Leadership Act, this presentation aims to pave the way for a more inclusive and equitable legal framework, one that empowers Khoi-San communities to assert their rights and reclaim their cultural heritage in the 21st century.

Inclusive Forest Governance and Managing Tribes in India: A Legal Pluralistic Analysis of Forest Rights Act 2006.

Dr. Shyama Prasad Rout, Indira Gandhi National Open University, New Delhi, India, 110068.
shyama2u@gmail.com

To understand the effects of legal pluralism at a variety of levels, there is a need to examine the ways in which the states regulate and respond to pluralism and its impact on communities and the social sector. In India the preservation of natural resources include within its fold the competing claims of humans on these resources for their sustenance and livelihood. Any approach for sustainable forest management in India must factor in the reality that many people living in and near the forests (tribes)- and depending on them - are among the poorest. Both minor forest produce (MFP) or non-timber forest produce (NTFP) are crucial for their survival. The mostly colonial legal regime governing preservation and use of forests has failed to reflect this understanding. Furthermore, over the last two decades, while the genuine forest dwellers (tribes) have lived in fear of eviction, mafias have encroached on forests and have alienated tribal land. There is a need to distinguish between forests dwellers and commercial exploitation of forest resources for timber and fuel wood. In the former case the so-called encroachment is a local and subsistence-driven activity, while in the latter case a widespread organized industry is largely driven by the mafia. The approach of law and policy to the two situations cannot be the same. In an attempt to make

forest governance inclusive, the Government of India introduced the Forest Rights Act 2006 wherein some of the customary rights of the tribes were recognized. The Act provides land rights to the forest dwellers, right to collect minor forest produce etc. However, the Act has conflicted with many old and existing Acts, Policies and Tribunals. While the new forest governance did come as a welcome step for forest dweller, after almost two decades it is time to assess who has benefitted from the new approach.

Legitimacy Challenges in Minicoy: Customary Systems in a State-Dominated Framework

Abel Job Abraham, Independent Researcher; affiliated with the Dakshin Foundation, Bangalore during the study, abeljobabraham@gmail.com

Minicoy, the southernmost island of the Lakshadweep archipelago, practices Islam, maintains a matrilineal inheritance system, and follows a personal law system based on Sharia. For centuries, its customary systems, including the Fisheries Jama'ath and village governance structures, have effectively managed individuals, land, and resources. However, increased exposure to external factors enabled by technological advancements and Minicoy's integration into the Indian Union post-colonial era, coupled with the state's expanding role in land and resource governance have diminished the community's reliance on collective action and the social capital offered by customary systems. Internal dynamics are also challenging the customary systems, with prioritization of socioeconomic goals by some members, dissatisfaction among the younger generation regarding inequity in rule enforcement, and political hegemony and partisan politics, weakening traditional institutions. Dissident members question the importance given by state institutions to customary leaders alongside elected state representatives. The state treats communal lands as public property and acquires them for development purposes without recognising customary ownership, further diminishing the customary system's legitimacy. The state leverages the mobilisation power of customary institutions but it does not provide formal recognition due to the community's limited demographic and political bargaining power. This lack of recognition and support undermines the legitimacy of customary systems, raising concerns about who seeks recognition and who gets representation within these frameworks. This paper presentation will explore how Minicoy's customary systems are dynamically evolving and transitioning under external pressures and internal conflicts, highlighting legitimacy concerns amid the increasing role of the state and the lack of formal recognition.

Janine Ubink, Van Vollenhoven Institute for Law, Governance and Society, Leiden University, j.m.ubink@law.leidenuniv.nl,

Abstract coming

Panel 7

Rights, Conflict, and Justice: Engaging with Legal Pluralism in Asia

Convenors: Sulistyowati Irianto, Faculty of Law, Universitas Indonesia: sulistyowati.ma@ui.ac.id, sulisirianto60@gmail.com; Masami Mori Tachibana, Kyoto Bunkyo University 森正美, masamimi@po.kbu.ac.jp; Pampa Mukherjee, Department of Political Science Panjab University Chandigarh, pmkh17@gmail.com

Culture, norms, colonization, social and economic history, have all played crucial roles in shaping many parts of Asian society. These factors have played an important role in contemporary Asia where customary norms and practices are intertwined with the evolving statutory laws. In this context, often conflicts arise,

and rights get redefined. These changes and evolving scenarios raise a pertinent question regarding justice, especially, "justice for whom?" Legal pluralism has shown connectivity between international and country specific laws in various countries. This is especially interesting for the post-colonial countries of Asia whose statutory legal systems have been significantly influenced by international laws. However, these statutory laws undergo a process of "translation," adapting to the history of customary practices and norms. Such translation is more contentious in the space where livelihoods are intertwined with social, cultural, religious and other customary practices and norms. K. Benda-Beckmann further explains the context when international law is linked to specific issues, especially regarding religion, environment, social, and gender justice in certain countries (K. Benda-Beckmann, 2022). Therefore, there are spatial features in legal pluralism discourse that need to be understood and analyzed. Way back in 1974, French philosopher Henri Lefebvre engaged with the production of space, especially the social production of space that deals with a triad of space, namely spatial practice (or perceived space), representation of space (or conceived space), and representational space (or lived space). This triad provides a perspective to unpack how customary practice and statutory laws interact, confront, and negotiate to shape and reshape the society. This panel welcomes a diverse range of papers that demonstrate how statutory laws interact with customary laws, including how international legal processes enter the territory of states. This can be observed in a variety of thematic issues such as human rights, environmental justice, gender justice, politics and democracy and even in rights and justice associated with livelihoods and food systems. In this panel, we intend to engage with these aspects of legal pluralism discourses shaping the political, social, and economic narratives in contemporary Asia.

Common Land, Rights and Gender in Punjab: Harmonizing statutory law and customary Practices, India

Pampa Mukherjee, Department of Political Science Panjab University Chandigarh,
pmkh17@gmail.com

There has been no denying the fact that land including common land, has been considered a main source of wealth, social status and power. However one finds that most of the studies on commons tend to discuss issues either in gender neutral terms or are largely focused on men, who tend to have disproportionate rights, ownership, or access with regards to resources. Due to influence of patriarchy and other social divisions, women have unequal access to different types of property regimes including commons. The gradual decline of common resources in recent years, due to numerous factors including the state, market and existence of diverse normative orders, both customary and statutory, impacted women in various ways. Empirical evidence shows that while in some instances declining commons have impacted women negatively, in others it has also forced them to come together to bring about change. Given this context, the presentation analyses the impacts of legal pluralism on women's land rights in Punjab India arguing that despite a progressive legal framework, efforts are still needed to fully achieve gender equitable and socially just outcomes on the ground. As far as common agricultural land is concerned, one finding is that tensions between statutory law and customary rules that are discriminatory towards women tend to prevail over the gender sensitive statutory provisions, undermining women's land rights in the region

Customary Law and the Administration of Justice in Northeast India: Access to Justice and Dispute Resolution Within Plural Justice Systems

Melody Hmangaimawi, PhD Candidate Department of Humanities and Social Sciences, IIT Madras, India hs19d010@smail.iitm.ac.in

The Sixth Schedule of the Indian Constitution provides provisions for administering justice in the autonomous tribal regions and councils in northeast India, primarily governed under customary law. The

coexistence of customary law and constitutional law in these regions can sometimes lead to conflicting claims of justice, consequently leading to concerns about access to justice. Access to justice is often studied in conjunction with Alternate Dispute Resolution (ADR) and dispute perspective studies. The study is based on the practical application of the dispute perspective model to identify access concerns and issues in the plural justice systems of the Mizo, Hmar and Kom tribes of northeast India. An analysis of the lived reality and practical application of theoretical approaches reveals the gap between theory and practice. ADR is especially significant for the case of tribal societies in Northeast India for three major reasons: the coexistence of state courts and customary courts, the ambiguous concept of justice in tribal communities, and the autonomy of administration under customary law. The communities included in the study have multiple and parallel forums of dispute resolution circumscribed by customary law, which may lead to conflicts in their interaction with constitutional law. Perceptions of justice in the communities under study can be dynamic and are not dependent on procedural justice but rather on retributive and restorative justice guided by customs. This leads to the subjective connotations of justice in tribal societies, which may differ across tribes depending on what is considered just in relation to the existing norms. In a scenario where the very notion of justice is contested and where multiplicities of justice exist, how does one formulate policies for equal access to justice? This question warrants a critical analysis of access to justice through the lens of intersectionality to devise alternative mechanisms for grievance redressal and resolution of disputes in areas administered under customary law. The research incorporates ethnographic observations and oral histories, substantiated by case studies, to explore inconsistencies in existing mechanisms and approaches to justice under customary law. The paper is situated on the backdrop of the debate on customary law vis-a-vis constitutional morality. It also highlights the need to incorporate traditional notions of justice in studies of legal reform in plural societies.

Heritage, livelihood and tourism in Uji tea production area in Japan

Masami Mori Tachibana, Kyoto Bunkyo University 森正美, Japan, masamimi@po.kbu.ac.jp

Cultural landscape is the newest category of the world cultural heritage. It does not only refer to things such as buildings and monuments, but also includes the "landscape" that has been inherited through the livelihood activities of the people in the area. It is recognized as a heritage site including the activities of the people through time. If we try to conserve and utilize a specific area and the activities of people there, including their livelihoods, as "heritage," it will be sometimes necessary to re-examine or change the way the space was used and the meaning it gave. At the same time, this will lead to reviewing and changing the rules of different levels and social norms regarding the ownership and use of space. This paper focuses on the Uji tea production area in the southern part of Kyoto Prefecture in Japan. It discusses Uji tea production as an agricultural activity, changes surrounding Uji tea consumption both in local and global markets, and the meaning given to the space by making the Uji tea production landscape a cultural heritage site. It deals with the transformation of rules and the politics of the interests of people with diverse positions. Tourism is also included in the analysis since it is one of the key factors to influence the attitudes and perception of the people.

The 'Impossibility' Of Modern Constitutionalism's Dialogue with Pluri-Legal Indian Civic Society - Inquiry and Reflections

Aditya Rawat, Assistant Professor (SS), School of Law (UPES Dehradun) & Doctoral Candidate, NALSAR Hyderabad; aditya.rawat@ddn.upes.ac.in; aditya.rawat013@gmail.com

Modern Constitutionalism is premised on legal homogeneity and hence has a chequered relationship with plurality. The relationship becomes messier when the gaze shifts to post-colonial civilizations wherein plurality has also potential of colonial construction. Indian Supreme Court's rights-based adjudications in

the last two decades manifest this tension wherein its ethos confronted value pluralism and moral pluralism of religion-based, caste-based, village-based, and tribe-based legal orders in India. As anecdotal evidence, The Court held the practice of *Khap Panchayat* (Caste Courts) and their engagement with 'honour killings' as unlawful. The *Khap Panchayats* across India curtly dismissed the legitimacy of the apex court to undermine them. Similarly, SC's uncomfortable and incongruent jurisprudence with religious pluralism (*Hijab* judgment, *beard in disciplinary forces* judgment, and *Sabarimala* judgment) all posit a pressing question about the 'legal centralist' tendency of modern Constitutionalism in the Global South. Peter Fitzpatrick, in *The Mythology of Modern Law*, argues that "one nation/state-one society- one law" is a site of myth-making. Indian Apex Court, empowered by the legitimacy of the Constitutional text, naively believes in this myth and the potential of this myth to address civilizational issues plaguing the pluri-legal Indian society. At the same time, India's heterogeneity is a labyrinth for disquisitions over plurality. Post-colonial and decolonial studies shed light on this labyrinth, but mainstream legal scholarship considers it a *cul-de-sac*. Through this paper, I intend to trace the 'origin stories' of tensions between Constitutionalism and legal pluralism in India and how those tensions shaped the epistemology of Indian Constitutionalism. It has rendered it further incapacitated to engage with 'other ways of being' and provide a pluri-legal society with 'equality of voices'.

The judge between law, justice and society

Sulistiyowati Irianto, Faculty of Law, Universitas Indonesia: sulistiyowati.ma@ui.ac.id, sulisirianto60@gmail.com

Since the beginning of the Reformation Era in 1998, Indonesia has endorsed many legal instruments and policies. Indonesia has also implemented development programs to ensure legal reform. However, it is apparent that judicial reform and legal practices are not yet moving on the right path. There are two main crucial problems that relate to the position of Indonesia's judges. The first problem is rooted within the existing legal framework for the independence of judges. The current regulations stem from the third amendment of the Indonesian Constitution. The existing legal instruments include regulations on the recruitment, promotion and transfer of judges, systems that lack much needed transparency and accountability. Judges are positioned as objects instead of as a subject of a certain administrative rank. The second problem involves judges who have mainly been placed in remote regions. The issues they face include lacking much needed resources and information – such as cutting-edge legal knowledge and instruments, sufficient supporting facilities, violence and insecurity in border and conflict areas, being far from home and family, as well as the high living costs in certain regions. These material and immaterial burdens impact how judges think and ultimately result in the lack of quality decisions. It is little wonder that many judges still position themselves as simply mouthpieces for the written law. This paper aims to explain the problems that Indonesian judges face by investigating the position of judges and its implication on law enforcement. How is the judge positioned by law? What are the implications of the judge's position on the judicial functions of settling disputes and ensuring the delivery of justice? How are politics and the historical background of the Indonesian judiciary reflected in the current limitations on the independence of judges? How does a judge's daily life constrain his or her performance?

Unraveling the Links between Human Rights and New Punitiveness

Dr. Adnan Sattar, Assistant Professor Shaikh Ahmad Hassan School of Law, Lahore University of Management Sciences, adnan.sattar@lums.edu.pk

While the diffusion of human rights norms has done a great deal of good in the world, the ideology of human rights, which has come to supplant other moral vocabularies in varied contexts including in the global South, has its fault lines and blind spots. This includes, most notably, its offensive role or the

‘sword function’ in relation to criminal law and punishment, to borrow the expression popularised by Françoise Tulkens, a former judge at the European Court of Human Rights. Drawing on evidence from Pakistan, this paper seeks to show that human rights discourse at least partly accounts for enhanced levels of punitiveness, especially in the context of legal responses to gender-based violence and child abuse. In appropriating and producing human rights talk, lawyers, legislators, and activists have imported into public discourse a secular, retributive orientation to justice. Human rights advocates have added their approving voices to the state’s tough-on-crime legislative agenda. The government, for its part, is now able to claim that it has plugged legal loopholes in the fight against impunity by introducing tougher sentences. The local articulations of human rights in the context of crime and punishment reproduce the silence within global human rights discourse on love, generosity, forgiveness, empathy, and imperfect obligations. The paper builds a case for a robust scrutiny of the conceptual soundness and societal implications of the anti-impunity doctrine as the key normative locus of the human rights movement as a necessary step in countering the coercive dimensions of human rights penalty.

Adat Law-Making of the Mollo Community: Marble Mining Prohibition and Beard Lichen Collection Restriction

Sartika Intaning Pradhani, Faculty of Law, Universitas Gadjah Mada – Indonesia
sartika@mail.ugm.ac.id

This paper aims to explore adat (customary) law-making with respect to both marble mining prohibition and Beard Lichens (*Usnea barbata*) collection by the Mollo Adat Law Community (ALC). The Mollo ALC issued a marble mining prohibition in 2000, while beard lichen collection was restricted in 2019. This research relies on interviews and observation over four months (June —September, 2021) in Timor Tengah Selatan Regency and Kupang Municipality, East Nusa Tenggara Province. Respondents included Mollo ALC’s adat functionaries and members, Non-Governmental Organization (NGO) activists, priests, and Civil Servants. Mollo ALC’s attitudes towards law and regulation implementation in their territory were varied and influenced by survival concerns. Adat law-making was consistently based on collective deliberation and adat functionaries’ reasoning was supported by subsequent development and change of the common economic and social-political context. Further, adat law could be compatible with other legal authorities. In the Mollo ALC experience, the threat of livelihood destruction resulted in a prohibition and/or termination ruling, while in a situation that brought local benefit, the adat law only restricted lichen collection. It demonstrates that adat law is open to change and is not an isolating process.

Shrinking Space for small-scale fishers: Reflections from Indian west coast

Amalendu Jyotishi, School of Development, Azim Premji University, Bengaluru,
amalendu.jyotishi@apu.edu.in

Artisanal and small-scale fisheries play an important social and economic role in the fish food systems. However, their workspace in the sea and the coast is threatened by numerous climatic and anthropogenic factors. Through an in-depth case study of Honnavara, Karnataka of India I attempt to understand the factors that are instrumental in shrinking the perceived, conceived and lived space of the small-scale fisher men and women. These factors include coastal erosion and accretions, increasing extreme weather conditions, hotel and tourism, eco-tourism beach and enclosure, cage culture in the estuary, utilization shift of fish from food to feed. These sets of evidence corroborate with Lefebvre’s ‘social production of space’ that explains the shrinking space for the small-scale fishers unjustly denying them from their customary rights.

Customary practices in everyday life: negotiating with transaction state services

Nazrul Haque, Faculty, School of Development, Azim Premji University, Bengaluru-562125,
nazrul.haque@apu.edu.in

Currency is considered as one of the authoritarian positions of the state. The final settlement with the state happens with this currency. However, in everyday life, in a geography where availability of currency might be scarce, how communities deal with transactions and how customary norms evolve to facilitate the process, how boundaries- principles of inclusion and exclusions are defined, how relationships are accepted or negated are interesting questions. Similar are examples such as accessing very high demand public services like booking a train ticket or collecting foodgrains through public distribution system in a country like India. We can see how people negotiate with long queues, and how norms evolve and get accepted even without any formal state arrangement. Through these snippets of cases from everyday practices, in this paper, I attempt to understand the customary norms in everyday life, establishment of these norms, and the system of justice and arbitration that runs parallel to the statutory justice system. These norms vary across space based on perceived, conceived, and lived space as described by Henri Lefebvre. Also, in the case of dispute and conflicts how people engage with multiple customary justice systems and pseudo statutory system that provides deeper understanding of shopping forum and forum shopping as explained by the work of K. von Benda-Beckmann.

Unequal Experiences: Legal Pluralism and Human Rights in Gujarat's Dried Fish Economy

Alan Diduck, The University of Winnipeg, a.diduck@uwinnipeg.ca; Kirit Patel, The University of Winnipeg, k.patel@uwinnipeg.ca; Mohammad Anas Khan, The University of Winnipeg anaskhan.law@gmail.com

Small-scale fisheries (SSFs) provide livelihood and food security to millions globally. One such SSF sector in India is the informal dried fish economy where women are a major workforce in post-harvest segments. Dried fish value chains in India are characterised by social, cultural, and legal diversity. Recognising the significance of SSFs, the SSF Guidelines explicitly call for a human-rights-based approach to developing SSF value chains. Operationalising human rights in SSFs necessitates attention to context and the lived experiences of the diversity of actors engaged in the value chain. In this paper, we describe how legal pluralism shapes the lived experience of human rights of various actors in the localised dried fish value chain in Valsad, India. Valsad's dried fish value chain represents social, cultural, and religious diversity of actors governed by multiple normative orders rooted in political, social, and cultural contexts. Drawing on ethnographic data, we highlight how power and social relations operating under a system of legal pluralism influence human rights issues, such as wage equality between genders, access to markets, inclusive decision-making, and fairness of dispute redressal mechanisms. It leads to different and unequal experiences of human rights for marginalised and vulnerable actors. Through this analysis, we highlight that the experience of citizenship, which connects human rights to agency, goes beyond formal legal status to include embodied intersectional social relations under intersecting normative orders. Hence, accounting for legal pluralism and situated experiences of citizenship is crucial to operationalising a human rights-based approach to development in SSF value chains.

Theresia Dyah Wirastrri

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Panel 8

Improving local justice, challenging court legitimacy? The case of “hybrid justice institutions”

Convenor: Wiebke Wiesigel, Institute of Anthropology, University of Neuchâtel; Van Vollenhoven Institute for Law, Governance and Society, Leiden University w.wiesigel@law.leidenuniv.nl

Though local customary or religious justice institutions in the Global South have often been lauded for their accessibility, they have also been criticised for discrimination based on gender, age, social class or religion (cf. Johnson 2018; McInerney and Ubink 2011). Aiming to improve the justice delivered in rural areas, legal development and state actors regularly make the case for different models of “hybrid justice institutions” that combine the accessibility of customary or religious courts with the legal standards and coercive apparatus of the state (cf. Clark and Stephens 2011; Dinda 2017; Kerrigan et al. 2012; Ubink and Mnisi Weeks 2017). In a legal pluralist setting, justice institutions shop for disputes and compete for financial, material, and symbolic resources (K. von Benda-Beckmann 1981). The courts therefore must make themselves navigate multiple ideologies and practices of justice and networks of social actors. Though the hybridity may be an opportunity to improve the justice delivered, it can also challenge institutional legitimacy as courts need to contend with sometimes-conflicting expectations from the state and religious or traditional leadership. Taking this tension as starting point, this panel focuses on the legitimacy of different forms of local hybrid justice institutions. It welcomes papers that discuss how such institutions negotiate their legitimacy, be it towards disputants, other state or customary dispute resolution forums, the judicial administration, and traditional or religious leaders.

Asantehemaa’s Traditional Court, Legal Pluralism and Justice Provision in Ghana.

Lydia Amoah, Institute of African Studies, University of Ghana, Lydiaamoah2003@gmail.com

African societies had established legal systems and laws to govern their people long before colonial powers set foot on African soil. The practice of customary arbitration was one such method. The effect of colonial laws is not unique to Ghana. The colonialists preserved the Ghanaian customs and laws whilst they imposed British common law. They permitted customary law to coexist with common law. Therefore, customary law was used in chief's native courts, while common law was utilized in colonial courts. Due to Ghana's status as a legal pluralist state, these two approaches continue to coexist. However, the recognition of male traditional authority at the expense of female traditional leaders was one of the negative effects of colonial rule and the drawback of colonial regulations in the history of traditional authority and customary law. Using ethnographic research techniques, and exploring the lived experiences of disputants, I question the challenges of customary law, the use of traditional courts such as the Asantehemaa’s Court and the effect on legal pluralism in Ghana. I contend that although Queenmothers have long handled customary conflicts such as those observed at the Asantehemaa's court, their areas of jurisdiction have received little acknowledgement. In this light, Ghanaian Queenmothers have agitated for recognition and inclusion in the House of Chiefs. They contend that, although Ghana endorses the SDG goals on gender equity, the historical marginalization of female traditional leaders has an impact on the roles that they play, including defending the rights of women and children under customary law.

“Studying up” in Zambian Local Courts: empirical findings and theoretical implications

Wiebke Wiesigel, Institute of Anthropology, University of Neuchâtel; Van Vollenhoven Institute for Law, Governance and Society, Leiden University, wiebke.wiesigel@unine.ch

The research that delves into issues of local justice in postcolonial contexts of legal pluralism mostly focuses on the experiences of litigants, the outcomes they can obtain and the “forum-shopping” they engage in. In my PhD in legal anthropology, I took a divergent perspective. Heeding Nader’s call to “study up”, I decided to concentrate on the practices, discourses, and experiences of justice-makers (e.g., magistrates) in Zambian Local Courts. These courts are “hybrid” in the sense that they combine elements from state justice with customary justice institutions. In this talk, I will reflect on this methodological choice and ask what researchers can learn about legal pluralism (in a broad sense) when studying up. Drawing on long-term ethnographic fieldwork that I conducted in dispute resolution forums in rural

Zambia, I will show how my focus on justice makers led me to a dynamic and relational understanding of customary and state justice, and how the two categories are intertwined. Throughout the justice-making process, Local Court employees engage in “boundary-work” to position themselves and the court they are attached to in relation to the surrounding Traditional Courts and higher state courts. By doing so, they also redefine what customary and state justice means. I will show how and why this boundary-work is taking place and what it says about the politics of justice-making in a postcolonial context from an anthropological perspective.

The Houses of Chiefs in Ghana and the Question of Concurrent Jurisdiction: From a Legal Perspective to Socio-legal Analyses

Ihassan Sulemana Anamzoya, PhD, Senior Lecturer, Department of Sociology, University of Ghana, Legon, asanamzoya@ug.edu.gh

Aside from the Supreme Court, the Houses of Chiefs in Ghana serve as the only courts mandated by constitution and statute to adjudicate on causes or matters affecting chieftaincy popularly referred to as chieftaincy disputes. In resolving such disputes, the Houses of Chiefs apply both customary and English laws and the Judicial Committees that adjudicate on these disputes are constituted by chiefs (custodians of tradition and custom) and legal counsel trained in the English law. This paper focuses on the hybridization of the House of Chiefs, how its adjudication process manifests its plural legal systems, plural personnel, and the attempt by the Ghanaian state to incorporate traditional institutions into modern state structures and to harmonize customary law and received English law into one state institution. The paper enriches scholarship of legal pluralism by wading into the debate regarding concurrent jurisdiction as earlier advocated for, by legal scholars who have argued that Ghana’s High Court has concurrent jurisdiction over matters affecting chieftaincy citing constitutional phraseologies. This paper supports this argument but from a socio-legal perspective concluding among others that legal pluralism hardly exists without forum shopping.

The Mufti of Greece: A case- study on the Intertwining of religious and secular law

Apostolos Paralikas, PhD Candidate, Legal Advisor at the Hellenic Ministry of National Defence (Greece), paralikas@law.uoa.gr; Anna Boumpa (Lawyer, DEA Public Law Université Paris 1 (France), Legal Advisor at the Hellenic Ministry of Culture (Greece), annaboumpa@yahoo.com

The case of the Mufti in Greece is an example of law and religion intertwining and a unique example of a European country allowing the application of Sharia Law. In Greece, all citizens must obey the law, as passed by secular institutions, such as the Parliament. In Greece today, Muslim law is applied as a special law for certain categories of relations, which overrides common law in cases covered by the former. The application of this law especially to Greek citizens of the Muslim religion who reside in Thrace was established following the international obligations that Greece undertook under the Athens Treaty of 1913 and the Treaties of Sevres of 1920 and Lausanne of 1923. The Mufti has jurisdiction over family, inheritance matters and personal relations, including marriages, divorces, alimony (nefaka), commissions, guardianships, Islamic wills and intestate succession. Therefore, in addition to his religious duties, which derive from the sacred Muslim law, and his advisory duties, the Mufti also exercises jurisdiction on Muslim Greek citizens of his district over the aforementioned family and inheritance law issues. However, the cases of family and inheritance law which fall within the jurisdiction of the Mufti are limited, as the Mufti is competent provided that the legal case concerns exclusively Muslims of Thrace. If one of the persons involved is non-Muslim, the Mufti ceases to have jurisdiction. However, Greek Muslim residents of Thrace have the right to choose between submitting to the jurisdiction of the Mufti and appealing to the competent court, whose jurisdiction is concurrent. Decisions issued by the Mufti in cases of contested jurisdiction cannot be enforced or constitute *res judicata* unless they are declared enforceable by the

Single Judge Court of First Instance. The court shall only investigate whether the decision was issued within the limits of the Mufti's jurisdiction and whether the provisions applied are contrary to the Constitution. According to the Single-Member Court of First Instance of Thrace, certain Mufti's decisions are not in accordance with the Constitution.

Panel 9

Pluralism, Colonial Modernities and Aboriginal/Indigenous Subjectivity

Convenor: Brendan Loizou, University of Sydney, bloi8385@uni.sydney.edu.au

There has been a shift in the colonial settler modernities that have impacted Aboriginal/Indigenous (A/I) peoples across the globe. This can be seen in recent observations such as by Margaret Davies, who points out that: "Suffice to say that any pluralised understanding of law cannot ignore the diversity of subjects in their multiple, embodied, overlapping and contested social sphere because the subject is both the creator and transmitter of law" (M. Davis Law Unlimited 2017 p7). This draws attention to the plight of the A/I 'subject' and attempts by them to 'transmit' their law. Has the modern nation state completely quelled and stifled the law of the A/I subject? Against this statement, it becomes clear that the current challenges facing A/I require an understanding of the diversity of 'laws' (customs) which have not been recognised nor supported by the modern state. The question whether the modern state authority is competent to engage with the nature of pluralism has yet to be properly examined and analysed. Leading to an evaluation of pluralism to support the diversity of A/I societies.

The Rule of Law with Indigenous Characteristics

René Provost, Centre for Human Rights and Legal Pluralism and Faculty of Law McGill University, rene.provost@McGill.Ca

The emerging practice of the administration of justice by Indigenous peoples in Canada raises fundamental questions about the nature and content of the rule of law. The rule of law enjoys a sort of evanescent permanence in legal discourse, perceived as the necessary but usually undiscussed foundation of any legitimate legal order, whether it be international or constitutional. Indeed, everyone seems to support the idea of the rule of law, from democracies to authoritarian regimes, from the global north to the global south, from capitalist societies to communist ones. In no small part, its global appeal reflects its nature as an essentially-contested concept, without any agreed content. There have been endless debates between partisans of 'thick' and 'thin' understandings of the rule of law, and among those defending universalist views and those permeated by local specificity, like the Chinese Communist Party's 'socialist rule of law with Chinese characteristics'. Despite the enormous range of views and positions, however, there is a common thread uniting nearly all discussions of the rule of law, in the central position occupied by the state. The restraining function of the rule of law must be applied to all sources of public authority in society. Thus, the precepts that are articulated with respect to the rule of law as attaching to the state must be reimagined so that they can also attach to the authority and laws of other actors, including Indigenous peoples. In the Canadian context, this calls for reimagining the rule of law so that it can bridge the claims of autonomy and dignity, or indeed sovereignty, of First Nations and the sovereignty of the Canadian state.

Vernacularization of Indigenous Human Rights in Vietnam

Ta Thi Thuy Duyen, Senior, Fulbright University Vietnam, duyenta0602@gmail.com

In 2007, Vietnam ratified the Universal Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous People. However, because indigenous people are not recognized in Vietnam, their rights have not been applied there. Due to the absence of a transnational consensus regarding the indigenous definition, there is room for interpretation with this concept. This article aims to learn about the process of vernacularisation of human rights, which focuses on transforming and translating international human rights principles into ideas that are acceptable in the local context, by illustrating the concept of indigeneity using the example of the Montagnard people in Vietnam. Given that the Montagnard having long lived in the central highlands of Vietnam with strong ties to the land and forest, international scholars and human rights organizations consistently refer to them as indigenous people. However, the government rejects the concept as appropriate in the context of Vietnam. The article focuses not only on common “vernacularisers”, such as the transfer of human rights to interior spaces, but also on the justification and discourse of governmental denial in translation of the concept in Vietnam. This argues that in cases of political and cultural complexity such as indigeneity, governments should be fully included as a factor in the vernacularisation of international human rights concepts. In addition, the article also offers a Socialist analysis and approach regarding ethnic and indigenous peoples.

Pluralism, Colonial Modernities and the Genealogy of First Nations Interpreters

Brandon Loizou, University of Sydney, bloi8385@uni.sydney.edu.au

In this paper I set out to outline what might be a new understanding of the creation of legal truths. These truths might then be better understood as representations of the beliefs, values and concepts that create the world around us. It might be asserted, that there are, in essence multiple/meta worlds. These worlds are not restricted by the *epistemology of modernity* nor of coloniality which has maintained this world but are existing in various stages and forms. I focus on First Nations people who act as interpreters. I use this term which captures other definitions, such as: Aboriginal; Indigenous/Indigene; and Tribal peoples. The approach I want to take is a consideration of legal pluralism as a tool (or device) that might offer a meaningful way to exploring these worlds. Thereby, considering the moments which define the legal ‘fabric’ of history which has and continues to shape these worlds with an emphasises on the creation of the First Nations interpreters and their role in the colonial matrix of power. On one hand it might be asserted that there has been a shift in the way the world as constructed by colonial settler modernities have impacted First Nations across the globe. This can be seen in a recent observation of Margaret Davies point that:

“Suffice to say that any pluralised understanding of law cannot ignore the diversity of subjects in their multiple, embodied, overlapping and contested social sphere because the subject is both the creator and transmitter of law.” (M. Davis Law Unlimited 2017 p7)

This draws attention to the plight of the First Nations ‘subject’ and attempts by them to ‘transmit’ their law: their world view. Against this statement, it becomes clear that the current challenges facing First Nations require an understanding of the diversity of ‘laws’ (customs) which have not been recognised nor supported by the modern state. The question whether the modern state authority is competent to engage with the nature of pluralism has yet to be properly examined and analysed. Leading to an evaluation of pluralism to support the diversity of First Nations societies. The representations of the subject and justifications for maintaining the subject as the ‘other’ is relevant to approaching the way in which “contingent facts” as Amia Srinivasa suggests, is “where we might find ourselves in a the space of possibility”.¹ The possibility to comprehend the nature of the representations we rely upon and the way we might be able to discover the way in which the beliefs values and concepts that are considered true form one moment in history, and which may, be re-represented.

Mabo Before and After

Agnes T.M. Schreiner LL.M, Ph D, University of Amsterdam, Law Faculty, General Jurisprudence Department, e-mail: a.t.m.schreiner@uva.nl

Eddie (Koiki) Mabo and others sued the State of Queensland. They won. The legendary court decisions (Mabo I and II) brought a shockwave over the land that was considered to be *terra nullius*. Common law is enriched with the 'native title'. Eddy Mabo, a lawman according to Aboriginal Law, was assisted by Anglo Australian lawyers. The plaintiff Eddy coincides with the lawman Koiki like a *Gestalt Switch*. In Aboriginal Law Koiki Mabo has to prove himself, assisted by relatives. In proving lawmanship the Aboriginal law comes to the fore. On the common law site native title was constrained by the Native Title Act 1993 and even more by the Native Title Amendment Act 1998. The *Gestalt Switch* applies to what came after: the perspective of settling once and for all on the Anglo-Australian site and the perspective of the Aboriginal law of negotiating on the other site.

The Global Land Rush and Climate Change: Customary Land Tenure Possibilities

Zvikomborero Chadambuka, Wayne State University, Detroit, zchadambuka@gmail.com

There has been a rise in very large-scale transnational commercial land acquisitions in the global south, notably in sub-Saharan Africa. Such acquisitions, often referred to as land grabs, accelerated especially sharply after the 2007-08 world food crisis. The issue of land grabs intersects with issues of climate change. Many climate change mitigation efforts—most notably the turn to biofuels— generate a huge demand for land that is then satisfied by land grabs. There is also the further concern that the land grabs themselves undermine climate change mitigation initiatives. Massive commercial agriculture is associated with deforestation as well as a turn towards monoculture, a land use option that generates extensive emissions. With a focus on countries in sub-Saharan Africa, this paper considers the possibilities of using customary law and tenure systems to limit land grabs and mitigate their negative environmental impacts, including impacts on the climate. Many of the countries which are targets in the global land rush are post-colonial countries which feature plural legal systems. They have a formal legal system, usually one introduced as part of the colonial enterprise and based on a western civil law or common law system. They also feature a customary/traditional legal system which, though in widespread use in some parts of the country—particularly rural areas, is often subordinate to the formal legal system. That legal system entails a separate governance framework as well as a customary land tenure regime. The existence of a customary legal framework, alongside the general legal framework, creates a different source of legitimate political governance. It also entails a different vision of property and land tenure. Both of these factors provide possibilities for resistance to potentially problematic transactions and for mitigation of such transactions' negative impacts. Two channels by which customary legal systems can also be used to resist large-scale land acquisitions and mitigate their negative social and environmental impacts are addressed. First is the idea that customary law governance frameworks create a local institutional framework that facilitates some resistance to power from the political centre, and so can resist some deleterious land transactions. Second is the notion that customary land tenure systems generally embody a different idea of property—an idea that is more communitarian. That idea can be engrafted onto property as understood within the country's legal system, so as to protect some access to essential resources for local communities, even in the wake of large-scale land transactions. More broadly, this discourse—notably including its tendencies against private alienation—can be deployed to exclude some transnational land transactions altogether. Both preclusion of transnational land transactions and engrafting of customary law-based communitarian notions into the understanding of property can also aid to ensure that space remains for customary land uses. This is significant as customary land uses also tend to have minimal negative impacts on local communities and on the environment, relative to the land uses associated with transnational land transactions.

Law as a reflex of ontological reality. A shaman as a judge

Magdalena Krysińska-Kaluźna, PhD, Institute of Ethnology and Cultural Anthropology, University of Wrocław, [magdalena.krysińska-kaluźna@uw.edu.pl](mailto:magdalenakrysińska-kaluźna@uw.edu.pl); krysińska@o2.pl

For indigenous peoples, the "reality" on the basis of which national courts issue their judgments is often distant from the ontological reality in which indigenous people live. This reality is associated with mythical events and characters that the "Western", "positivist" concept of explaining the world in no way takes into account. Positive, national law is usually based on Enlightenment rationality, and traditional (customary) law of indigenous peoples is usually not. The ancestors and the mythical events are bearers of the truths and of the knowledge that guided and often continues to guide the life of the indigenous communities. In this way the Amazonian indigenous world is definitely not demarcated and divided between human and non-human and the "acts" of the people are not limited only to the activities they do when they are in their human body. A good example of how Amazonian indigenous people perceive the interdependence between the human and non-human world, "visible" and "invisible," supernatural beings, shaman and others that function in these worlds, is the healing process. During this process the shaman often decides who is to blame for a disease or other disaster. Using several examples from Latin America and especially, from the Amazon region I will indicate the link between indigenous law, or customary law, and shamanic practices as well as the social consequences of this link.

Opportunities and Challenges for Legal Pluralism in the Face of Prevalence of Neurodisability Among Indigenous Justice-Involved Children in the Northern Territory, Australia

Clement Ng, Scientia, PhD Candidate, University of New South Wales, Australia, ncwclement@gmail.com

Over 90% of children detained in the youth justice facilities in Northern Territory, Australia are Indigenous. At least one-third of these children grew up in remote Aboriginal communities, with others from regional and urban centres. Together, they represent a diverse range of Aboriginal customs, languages and cultures. Yet, there is one mainstream system that governs juvenile justice administration and Aboriginal perspectives on justice and due process are largely ignored, particularly since the discontinuance of community courts in 2010. Recent studies have also revealed that neurodisability and multi-neurodisabilities are prevalent among Indigenous children who are involved in the justice system. This poses significant challenges to juvenile justice administration given its heavy reliance on cognitive and verbal competence. Arguably, the prevalence of neurodisability also creates significant barriers to implementing a pluralist approach to juvenile justice administration given the difficulties associated with communication and fundamental cognitive functioning. This presentation will draw on a number of case studies from a court file audit conducted with respect to 755 children's court files to illustrate the relevant issues. Notwithstanding these challenges, this presentation will also attempt to identify a number of significant opportunities such as the re-establishment of Community Courts, Aboriginal Justice Agreement and potential Treat(ies) with Aboriginal people and discuss their relevance in realising Indigenous children rights and embedding Indigenous values in administering juvenile justice in the future.

Colonial Modernities and Indigenous Subjectivity: Analysing Evidentiary Practices in the Human Rights Committee and Indigenous Responses

Prof. Dr. Reetta Toivanen, University of Helsinki, Finland, Reetta.toivanen@helsinki.fi

What is considered a fact in an individual communication processed by the Human Rights Committee (henceforth HRC or the Committee)? In the absence of an International Human Rights Court, the HRC is widely accepted to be the UN's most authoritative human rights monitoring mechanism. Yet little is known about the 'jurisprudence' it produces in response to individual communications against states that

have signed the relevant optional protocol. This chapter explores the Committee's evidentiary practices via the case studies of *Sanila-Aikio v. Finland* (2018) and *Näkkäljärvi et al. v. Finland* (2018), concerning the inclusion of new voters in the electoral roll of the Sámi Parliament. This paper analyses the processes of translation through which evidence becomes distanced from Committee members as they deliberate on individual communications, and it questions how the veracity of material is ascertained. Particular attention is paid to the role of intermediaries, namely, the legal counsel who represented the authors of the two communications and thus helped translate their experiences into the expected human rights vernacular. Moreover, the paper addresses the danger of essentializing Indigenous subjects within legal frameworks, highlighting how the imposition of rigid evidentiary standards can obscure the complex, lived realities of Indigenous communities.

The paper concludes with reflections on how the evidentiary regime of the HRC produces and supports certain subjectivities while downplaying and eliminating others. It underscores the need for a nuanced approach that recognizes the diverse and multifaceted identities of Indigenous peoples, rather than reducing them to monolithic legal subjects.

Panel 10:

Church law and state law in the Global South

Convenors: Prof. Dr. René Pahud de Mortanges, Fribourg University/Switzerland, rene.pahuddemortanges@unifr.ch and Prof. Dr. Leon van den Broeke, TUU/VU Amsterdam/The Netherlands, cvandenbroeke@tukampen.nl

In the course of migration and colonisation, catholic and protestant church law have spread around the world, also gaining a foothold in the countries of the Global South. There they came into contact not only with indigenous legal systems, but also with state law, which, depending on the prevailing religion and political concept, had and still have a different approach to it. This raises all sorts of questions regarding legal pluralism. It is often state law, which influences and corrects church law. This we see when it comes to the legal status of religious people, but is also relevant in the constitutional set up of the churches. Whether one belongs to a state religion or a minority religion and whether the state takes a pro- or anti-religious approach not only has an influence on the life and visibility of churches, but also, for example, on their constitution and the organisation of their offices. A legal pluralistic approach therefore makes the transnational comparison of church law systems particularly valuable and fruitful.

Experiencing Multiple Normative Temporalities: The Secularization Processes of Nuns in XIXth Century Peru

Armando Guevara Gil, Universidad para el Desarrollo Andino jguevara@udea.edu.pe

The idea that the XIXth Century newly born nation-states in Latin America sought the elimination of legal pluralism and jurisdictional complexity, so characteristic of the Spanish colonial territories, is prevalent (Benton and Ross 2013; Decock 2017; Goodale 2008; Sieder et al. 2019; in general, Benda-Beckmann and Turner 2018). However, a more subtle and nuanced picture emerges when this overarching statement is contrasted with the historical transformations of the normative configurations of this period. As a case in point, nuns who filed suits for obtaining their secularization in Church and State courts were subject to different bodies of law (e.g., Ecclesiastical, liberal, enforceable old Spanish legislation). In my paper, I study how these multiple normative and jurisdictional temporalities conditioned the petitions and strategies of the women who sought to free themselves from their perpetual vows. And, even after secularization, they were subject to competitive normative temporalities from civil and ecclesiastical authorities. Thus, their experience shows how the configuration of conflictive normative and jurisdictional temporalities was part and parcel of the Peruvian XIXth Century nomos.

Reformed Church Order in Indonesia

Dr. Lazarus Purwanto, Sekolah Tinggi Filsafat Theologi Jakarta, Indonesia,
lazarus.purwanto@gmail.com

This paper will elaborate the church polity and other issues faced by churches in Indonesia from three points that are related to one another:

- church structure and leadership in all 'levels' which tends to be centralized and hierarchical.
- the church's missional identity in a multi-context and multi-complex society.
- the life and ministry of the church as local community that has been primarily disrupted by the Covid-19 Pandemic

Church order and Human Rights in Malawi: Soulmates or Antagonists?

Dr. Willy Zeze, Regional Coordinator for Theological Education by Extension in Malawi (TEEM),
willy.zeze@gmail.com

This paper will deal with

- the Constitutionality of the Church Order of the CCAP Nkhoma Synod in Malawi
- some Tendencies of Episcopatism in the Presbyterian System of Church Government
- the Attitude of the Youth on the uses of Church Order
- the Correct Relationship between Parties and Governing Parties in Malawi: A Historical Perspective 1964-2022
- the Practicality of Parity among Church Office Bearers
- the Embodiment of Christ's Headship and Human Headship in Church Polity Practice.

Reformed Church Order in Zambia

Godfrey Msiska, Adjunct Lecturer of Church History and Church Polity at Centre for Christian Mission Seminary in Zambia (location Kitwe) Zimbabwe, gmsiska2000@yahoo.com

This paper will deal with:

- reception of the Church Order of Dort on the continent of Africa (1619-2019)
- church order and missional church polity: challenges and opportunities of missional ecclesiology and missional church polity
- church polity and ecumenical church polity (influence of ecumenical church polity on decision making procedures et cetera): challenges and opportunities
- court cases and the church: Assess judicial implications of any court case lodged against church from reformed background
- globalization, challenges and opportunities with regard to church polity and church order.
- discipline of ministers of the Word and sacraments and the Labour Act.
- non-compliance of provisions in church orders of reformed churches: Case studies
- power of major assemblies to execute decisions in lower assemblies or in case of misconduct.

Panel 11

The Dynamics of Customary (Adat) Law and Its Relations towards the Religious Law, National (State) Law and International Law in Preserving and Protecting the Constitutional Rights of Indigenous People

Convenors: Asosiasi Pengajar Hukum Adat (APHA) Indonesia (Indonesian Adat Law Teachers Association), apha.sekretariat@gmail.com (cc. laksanto@gmail.com; rina.yulianti@trunojoyo.ac.id)

The existence of indigenous peoples in various parts of the world with all its dynamics and challenges continues to encourage the international community to produce various frameworks and norms to strengthen the protection and recognition of indigenous peoples. However, it cannot be denied that the conception and regulation of indigenous peoples in the international legal framework continues to experience dynamic developments that require countries to make adjustments in their domestic laws. Although many studies on indigenous peoples have been prepared, the implementation, recognition and protection of their laws both at home and abroad have not been fully fulfilled. In Indonesia, for example, until now there is no specific and comprehensive legal instrument on Indigenous Peoples that can provide clear guidance on their recognition and protection, so there are still debates that have implications for the recognition and implementation of legal protection of indigenous peoples. With regard to the above, APHA Indonesia in this panel needs to discuss the direction and existence of indigenous peoples and the application of customary (adat) law in various aspects and their relationship to religious law, national (state) law, and international law, such as the issue of state responsibility for the existence of indigenous peoples and their natural resources or ulayat rights, including the fulfilment of the rights of women and children of indigenous peoples, the development of customary (adat) economic law, aspects of customary (Adat) justice and legal politics of fulfilling the rights of indigenous peoples and others.

Transactions on Land and Apartment Rights: Between Business Practice Facts and Adat Norms

Iwan Erar Joesoef, Universitas Pembangunan Nasional Veteran Jakarta, iwan.erar@upnvj.ac.id

In this research, the legal accommodation of business practices pertaining to Land and Apartment Rights in Indonesia are assessed based on documentary evidence. Land and Apartment Rights refer to Western Law whilst the Indonesia Land Law (including Apartment Law) is based on Adat Law. Under adat, any land rights transaction is "terang, riil dan tunai" ("transparent, real and cash"), which means that the transaction should be in cash, real and with delivery in front of a Land Deed Officer (Pejabat Pembuat Akta Tanah (PPAT)). But a legal problem arises as to how the developer can sell the Apartment ("strata title") to the consumer with pre-payment (indent) when the Apartment is not yet constructed or is under construction or in the planning stages. The findings of this research is that the developer sells the Apartment through Pre-Project Selling, under which the Bank Institution asks the Developer for a Buy Back Guarantee. This type of transaction is running expeditiously in the business community. The conclusion of this research is that the transaction should be in front of PPAT by issuing a fair Pre-Agreement (Perjanjian Pengikatan Jual Beli_PPJB).

The Policy in Recognition of Indigenous Peoples Through Ratification of the Draft Bill on Indigenous Peoples

Prof. Dr. St. Laksanto Utomo S.H, M.Hum, Law Faculty, Bhayangkara University of Jakarta Raya, laksanto@gmail.com

This paper examines policies recognizing indigenous peoples through the ratification of the Indigenous Peoples Bill. Article 18B paragraph (2) of the 1945 Constitution recognizes and respects the existence of indigenous peoples conditionally: they must still exist, align with Indonesian societal development, and comply with the principles of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia as regulated by law. The Indigenous Peoples Bill, which aims to implement this constitutional article, has been part of the National Legislation Program since 2014 but remains unfinished. Analysis reveals that ratifying this bill is crucial for restoring Indigenous Peoples to their rightful status. It would act as an "umbrella law" for all policies

and regulations related to Indigenous Peoples and their rights. The bill's ratification would shift the perspective on Indigenous Peoples from regulation to protection, transforming recognition from a formalist approach to an organic one. The bill aims to transition the state's role from merely recognizing Indigenous Peoples to actively protecting, respecting, and realizing their rights. Given its importance, the constitutional authority of the House of Representatives of The Republic of Indonesia and the government should promptly pass the Indigenous Peoples Bill to ensure the protection and guarantee of the rights of indigenous peoples.

Prof. Dr. Rr. Catharina Dewi Wulansari

Abstract missing

Improving The Common Understanding of Judges in Deciding Cases on The Rights of Indigenous Peoples through Teaching Legal Skills in Candidate Judge Education

Rina Yulianti, Law Faculty, Universitas Trunojoyo Madura, rina.yulianti@trunojoyo.ac.id

Indigenous Peoples are not favored by regulation in proving written ownership of their natural resources. It is quite difficult for Indigenous Peoples whose laws are characterized as unwritten. Judges of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Indonesia confirmed that the weakness of indigenous peoples when facing disputes is that they do not have written evidence. This should not be an excuse for judges in deciding cases when relying on adat law whose style is not written. This centralized/unpluralistic ideology of judges must be corrected. The Association of Customary Law recommended the need for customary law to be included in the curriculum of the Supreme Court Education and Training Centre. Therefore, educating the pluralistic ideals of judges must start early, when they receive education and training for prospective judges. This strategy should be carried out by the Supreme Court, with a teaching legal skills approach that can stimulate prospective judges to be more active and critical in resolving cases involving customary law vs state law. Designing a learning policy model for customary law material with a teaching legal skills approach so that candidates in dealing with cases have an ideology of legal pluralism. Thus it is expected to prepare progressive judges without the dominance of state law. The teaching legal skills approach is very relevant to problem-based learning. Teaching legal skills on adat law material in the education and training of candidate judges so that there is general agreement in dealing with cases of the rights of indigenous peoples.

Panel 12: Legal Pluralism, Frontiers of Knowledge, and Other Fields

Convenor: Tine Suartina, BRIN – Research Center for Society and Culture, t.suartina@hotmail.com

As a result of societal and global processes, the relevance of the concept and reality of legal pluralism has grown in the contemporary context. To come to a comprehensive understanding of the empirical reality of legal pluralism, several other disciplines must be taken into account to understand the relationship with issues such as politics, the environment, formal authority (governance), and so on. The perspective can no longer be comprehended in and of itself from a restricted or limited legal aspect because, unavoidably, there are several facets, including non-legal aspects, that can lead to or influence contemporary legal pluralism. This circumstance establishes a new form or foundation of legal pluralism knowledge. The lens of frontiers and interdisciplinary studies is essentially helpful to see new and expanded juxtapositions of legal pluralism empirically by openly considering other areas or aspects. Benefits can come from a better ability to explain social phenomena and complexities in terms of plural legal systems that were not available in the past. The direction may consider the discipline's parallel connections to other fields along with various levelling including local, national, and transnational dimensions. We invite papers on legal

pluralism that examine and explore the context, application, evolution, and linkages with any factors or areas. The presented papers will serve to provide valuable insights into the conception, development, and evolution of contemporary legal pluralism through various stages. This panel aims to provide innovative perspectives on today's legal pluralism.

Conditional Consent to Sexual Relations

Mini Saxena, SOAS University of London, ms194@soas.ac.uk

Over the past 5-10 years, several scholars and judges across mostly Global North jurisdictions have attempted to address the complex issue of how the law should respond to conditional sexual consent. Conditional consent to sexual relations occurs when someone puts explicit or implicit conditions on their consent to sexual relations – for example, that their partner wear a condom or pay them afterwards. Scholarship on the legal treatment of conditional consent has burgeoned recently, but with no conclusive solutions. Current approaches to conditional consent are limited to academic and doctrinal criminal law approaches and very little empirical work. Conditional consent has been most deeply thought about and engaged with in the UK. This paper is a literature review of historic UK case law and academic scholarship on conditional consent. The paper argues that there has historically been judicial incoherence and bias in which conditions have had legal consequences and who can be a survivor, and a complete lack of clarity as to on what basis courts have adjudicated certain conditions to be ‘minor’ and others to be ‘major’. Current literature assumes that legal solutions for conditional consent can succeed on a merely conceptual level and therefore are universally applicable, without accounting for social contexts or non-legal or non-State conceptions of justice based on legal pluralism. Using the above arguments, I advocate for an empirical analysis of conditional consent in the Global South, positing that legal responses to conditional consent cannot be understood without understanding socioeconomic contexts, which vary widely.

Ethnic Housing and the Question of Legal Pluralism: The Case of Lampung Pepadun's *Nuwo Tuho* in Indonesia

Herlindah, The Faculty of Law, Brawijaya University, Malang, Indonesia, herlindah@ub.ac.id

This study explores the complexities of ethnic housing, cultural heritage, and property rights within Lampung Pepadun's customary legal system. Indonesian customary law (*Hukum Adat*) is integral to the national legal framework, complementing positive law by addressing legal gaps. However, the dichotomy in land law, which separates land ownership from buildings and structures unless explicitly agreed otherwise, creates significant ambiguities. Using a legal ethnographic approach, this study investigates the ethnic housing rights of *Nuwo Tuho*, the traditional houses of Lampung Pepadun, in Kotabumi District, North Lampung Regency. Despite being classified as private property under formal law, *Nuwo Tuho* functions as communal property within Lampung Pepadun's kinship and inheritance systems. This duality highlights the necessity for a legal pluralist understanding of property rights in the context of ethnic housing and cultural heritage preservation. The customary building rights of *Nuwo Tuho* encompass the use and management of the property for the extended family, adhering to the principle of *pi'il pasangiri*. This principle emphasizes the importance of familial ties and responsibilities in managing communal property for the benefit of the extended family. *Nuwo Tuho* is traditionally passed to the eldest male heir upon marriage, or to a designated female or adopted male in the absence of a direct male heir. It cannot be leased or sold because the alienation of *Nuwo Tuho* is considered to critically impact cultural identity and means of subsistence.

Recognition of women prisoners' experiences as a site of power for the promotion of citizenship and rights

Chipo Mushota Nkhata, University of Zambia, chipo.nkhata@unza.zm

Felicity Kayumba Kalunga, University of Zambia, felicity.kalunga@unza.zm

Statutory law is a widely recognised site of power used by or against vulnerable groups. Many vulnerable groups like women, persons with disabilities, and prisoners, have had various aspects of their rights protected through legislation. Some of these vulnerable groups have actively participated in the development of written rules as a means of asserting their citizenship. In the context of prison regulation, women inmates are among the most vulnerable populations that are excluded from participating in the development of written laws. In addition to the written laws, several unwritten norms and practices, that, have attained the status of law from the inmates' perspective, have evolved. These norms of practice have had the effect of varying and, in some instances, contradicting the written regulations. These unwritten norms and practices are however hardly recognised by the authorities and scholars when evaluating laws governing prisons. This paper uses the example of women prisoners' participation in health-related decisions in Zambia to evaluate the role of law in facilitating women inmates' active citizenship and enjoyment of rights in Zambia. It analyses the empirical experiences of women inmates in Zambia in using 'law' to practice active citizenship and assert their rights. These experiences demonstrate the plurality of laws obtaining in correctional settings as an example of the empirical reality of pluralism in institutions of formal authority. The paper argues that this plurality of laws deserves equal recognition in serving as a site of power for the promotion of prisoners' citizenship and rights' enjoyment.

Addressing gender violence in the Pakhtun regions of Pakistan: the power of statutory law, tribal norms and Islamic notions

Neha Ali Gauhar, PhD candidate, Van Vollenhoven Institute for Law, Governance and Society, Leiden University, na.gauhar@gmail.com

Swara is a longstanding Pakhtun custom in which blood feuds are resolved by giving girls, often underage, in marriage to the aggrieved family as compensation for crimes committed by male members of the girl's family. Despite Pakistan's commitment to various international human rights treaties, including the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women, which explicitly prohibits forced and child marriages, it is estimated that 180 Swara cases are reported annually in the country. This paper will explore the intricate interplay between Islamic law and local cultural norms and its interrelation with formal law. Additionally it will analyse the position of international human rights organizations on these practices, the solutions they propose and effectiveness of these approaches. In particular, the following key questions will be addressed: What is the stance of international human rights bodies on customary justice and Islamic law particularly in the global south? Are the strategies taken by these human rights bodies adequate to address discriminatory customary norms in Pakistan? How has the local approach countered Swara cases, and do they align with the policies of state and international bodies? By raising these issues, the study seeks to highlight the challenges and opportunities in finding a balance between statutory codes, religious principles, and customary norms. The aim is to develop effective strategies for eliminating anti-women practices in the Pakhtun region of Pakistan. Through this examination, the study hopes to contribute to the broader discourse on international human rights, legal pluralism, and the eradication of gender-based discrimination in customary practices.

Contemporary Juridical Legal Pluralism and Politics of Diversity in Indonesia

Tine Suartina, Research Centre for Society and Culture, Indonesia National Research and Innovation Agency (BRIN), t.suartina@hotmail.com

This paper uses a socio-legal approach and the politics of law to critically examine how state or government authorities implement legal pluralism acknowledgment, in addition to providing an extended discussion of contemporary juridical legal pluralism—one of the types of legal pluralism that Griffiths (1986, 2015) explained besides empirical legal pluralism. Considering the Indonesian example and the major political shifts brought about by the global revival movement in the Reform era in 1998–1999, the recognition of communities and customary law by local governments, the establishment of *adat* villages, and the status of *adat* forests all acknowledge the existence of customary (*adat*) law. Formalization and the compliance of *Adat* communities with the requirements have been selected as the acknowledgement mechanisms. Although the methods for managing diversities appear to be improving, they are inevitably political and have led to certain unexpected consequences, like an administratively burdensome and asymmetrical relationship between the communities (the applicants) and the formal authority (the benefactor for recognition, approval, and formal rule-making parties), as exemplified by a bottleneck situation in the process of local government approval and regulation-making. Formalization and formal acknowledgment serve a double-edged formal authority position: as mechanisms for a serious check to offer the acknowledgment, or truly politics. Nevertheless, even though the communities that advocate official acknowledgment understand it as a political process, the empirical plural legal order itself does not rely on that authority's recognition. This shows a continued duality awareness in the communities, for both formal and empirical purposes.

Panel 13

Science and Technology Studies and Legal Pluralism

Convenor: Bertram Turner, Max Planck Institute for Social Anthropology, turner@eth.mpg.de

While science and the law are often mutually reinforcing domains, scientific and technological change is challenging legal orders and legal institutions on a broad front. This panel aims to further explore the concept of Legal Pluralism (LP) as an analytical tool in the field of Science and Technology Studies (STS). Currently, the study of law and STS (L-STs) concentrates primarily on the law of the state and institutions of global governance. A more sophisticated look at complex legal configurations is needed. The panel seeks empirical and theoretical contributions as to the ways that law, science, and technology intersect in plural legal configurations and how they are linked with processes of law production at various scales. Differentiated global spaces are interconnected through law and science and technology co-production, as when mutually reinforcing technology and law are expanding across the planet. New models of ordering in health, food safety, energy, security, nature conservation, communication, digitalization (AI) and transport rely heavily on technoscience and the normativity it produces integrating plural legal configurations. We invite topics across a broad range of interests: Development; land, ocean and water management; food safety; security and territorial control; risk; policing, forensics; mapping (zoning, urban deregulation); technologies of knowledge transfer, knowledge co-production; quantification and data indexing; taxonomies and legal measurement; digitalization and AI, technical assistance and more.

Legal and Techno-Normative Entanglements in Indonesia's Developmental State

Tanius Sebastian, Faculty of Law, Parahyangan Catholic University, Bandung, Indonesia
tanius.sebastian@unpar.ac.id

The main interest of this paper lies in the connection between legal pluralism, legal theory, and development. My point of departure is a question about the nature of legal science or *ilmu hukum* in Bahasa Indonesia: is it a science? Arguably, this question has already been existing in the heart of Indonesian (post)colonial jurisprudential discourse, since the intellectual legacy of a Dutch prominent jurist, Paul Scholten (1875-1946), took root in Netherlands East Indies legal education. Drawing on the

Legal Pluralism and Science and Technology Studies (LP & STS) approaches, especially from the concepts of translation and infrastructure (Turner and Wiber, 2022), I will discuss that question by studying the techno-normative entanglements in development projects in Indonesia. The primary goal here is to analyse the way in which legal technique (Michaels and Riles, 2022) functions and how legal reasoning, scientific expertise, and power interacts. To that end, there several steps to be pondered on. First, I choose the issues of public health policy during the COVID-19 pandemic and natural resources management. As case studies, I take Bandar Lampung city (located in south cost island of Sumatra) as an illustration for the former, while Bandung city (the capital of West Java) for the latter. Second, I examine how sidelining of science and technology, instrumentalization of law, and developmental progress are carried out by the government and state. Here, the above-mentioned LP & STS concepts will be contextualized. And finally, the practices of knowledge will be discerned from those case studies, and I hope that that will couch a critical reflection: is Indonesian legal science a science?

Legal Pluralism as a lens to analytically engage with the “patchwork quilt” of cross-border police cooperation in Europe: The case of Police and Custom Cooperation Centers in information exchange

Monika Weissensteiner, Marie Skłodowska-Curie postdoctoral fellow, School of International Studies, University of Trento, Italy, m.weissensteiner@unitn.it

Cross-border police cooperation in the European context has frequently been described by policing scholars as being regulated by a “fragmented legal terrain” or legal “patchwork quilt” (inter alia Sheptycki 2001): plural legal configurations, indeed. In this presentation I focus on one instrument, Police and Custom Cooperation Centres. Initially set up in border-regions as a “tool of local collaboration”, centres bring under one roof the law enforcement authorities of (neighbouring) countries. The joint centres’ primary task consists of formal quick information exchange. While STS and European critical security study scholars have addressed for example the drive towards interoperability between EU databases, in this case, unpacking plural legal configurations and how they are “lived in practice” enables to interrogate a distinct form of interoperability-in-practice, within what emerges through the analytical lens of legal pluralism as a differential legal geography of data mobility. Drawing on the emic concepts of the “border-strip” and of the “red thread”, the geographical and functional extension of some centres’ tasks, provides productive insights into dynamics and politics of scale within the EU security architecture.

Shaping Malaysian Tech-Laws: Influences from Abroad

Siti Liyana Azman, International Islamic University Malaysia, l.azman@live.iium.edu.my

This paper analyses Malaysian technology laws from 1996-2024. Using process tracing methods, I investigate (1) the extent of foreign influences onto Malaysian technology laws and (2) methods of localization. Malaysia technology laws has undergone three stages; Early Period (1996-1998), the Post-Convergence Period (1999-2020), and the AI Boom (2021-2024). In the Early Period the Malaysian government prioritized IT infrastructure expansion. American laws (e.g. the repealed Utah Digital Signature Act and Federal Telecommunications Act 1996) heavily influenced legislative developments. This paper posits Malaysia’s underlying tech-governance philosophy was “*Move Fast, Build Quickly.*”, a Malaysian variant of Silicon Valley’s “*Move Fast, Break Things.*” Malaysia crafted its unique local convergence model by setting up the world’s earliest convergence regulator, the Multimedia and Communications Commission. During the Post-Convergence Period, legislative activity became stagnant. Malaysia continued to carry outdated laws from the 1990s into the millennium out of fear of restricting IT advancement. In the AI boom period Malaysia exhibits legal pluralism by benchmarking against AI governance standards by European Union, OECD, UNESCO, and the World Economic Forum.

Malaysia's tech-governance philosophy evolves to *Move Fast, Build Quickly, Remain Internationally Relevant*. The National AI Ethical Guidelines cites the primacy of *Rukun Negara*, Federal Constitution and Islamic values, but omits strategies to bridge local laws with international standards. With the fixation of being internationally relevant, Malaysia has underexplored ways to localize self-imposed international expectations. This paper provides insight for policy makers, stressing the importance of studying a country's legislative history to avoid haphazard legal transplants of foreign frameworks.

Legal Personhood for Artificial Intelligence: A Hohfeldian Analysis of Rights and Responsibilities

Mohammad Alvi Pratama, Faculty of Law, Universitas Pasundan, alvi.pratama@unpas.ac.id

The emergence of Artificial Intelligence (AI) as an integral part of modern society raises the critical question of its legal personhood: should AI be considered a legal person? This study investigates the feasibility and implications of granting AI legal personhood through the lens of Wesley Newcomb Hohfeld's analytical framework. The main problem addressed is the ambiguity in defining the rights and responsibilities of AI within current legal systems, particularly Indonesian legal systems. The purpose of this research is to provide a structured analysis of potential legal relationships involving AI, identifying the rights, privileges, powers, and immunities that could be applicable. The research method applied here is methodologically qualitative, whereby this research paper deconstructs the legal status which AI could possibly have through its legal texts, case law, and academic insights to dissect AI's potential legal standing. Hohfeld's matrix is applied to conceptualize AI's legal interactions, identifying correlatives and opposites of legal entitlements. The hypotheses are: (1) AI can be assigned certain rights and duties analogous to those of natural and corporate persons, and (2) Hohfeld's framework can effectively clarify these legal relationships. This research aims to contribute to the legal discourse by providing a clear, analytical foundation for future legislative and judicial considerations regarding AI's legal status. It seeks to balance technological advancement with ethical, philosophical and legal norms, ensuring AI integration into society aligns with established legal principles.

Panel 14

Legal pluralism and Earth laws in a more-than-human world

Convenor: Helen Dancer, University of Sussex, H.E.Dancer@sussex.ac.uk

From legal personhood and rights of nature, to multispecies normativities, ecocide, the well-being of future generations and environmental human rights, a new wave of activism is producing legal reform for climate justice, the protection of biodiversity, human and planetary health. Such developments have been galvanised through dynamic, fluid and transnational networks of activists, Indigenous Peoples, judges, lawyers, scientists, community actors, artists and philosophers, who approach the issues from a variety of ontological, ethical, disciplinary and practical perspectives. Normative contestations among this plurality of knowledges and actors, and processes of interlegality, are resulting in hybrid legal forms and paradigm shifts in law and practice at various scales. The aim of this panel is to explore the theoretical, creative and practical insights that legal pluralism scholars can offer in this highly dynamic area of legal change. Papers are encouraged on a variety of issues and geographical contexts: from rivers, forests and mountains, to animals, Indigenous Peoples' cosmologies, artificial intelligence and intergenerational relationships. They might for example, explore how, in any given context, interlegality across different scales of law, custom, cosmology, scientific and legal theories, or multispecies relationships have shaped the outcomes of legal cases or the development of legislation. To what extent are new developments in Earth laws serving to decolonise relationships between people and the state, and between human and nonhuman? What does empirical research tell us about how these legal innovations are working in practice at local, national and international scales? How is legal pluralism studies developing in this transdisciplinary space?

The rights of rivers as glocal legal pluralism. The case of the Marañón river in Peru

Patricia Urteaga-Crovetto, Profesora Principal, Departamento Académico de Derecho Pontificia Universidad Católica del Perú, purteaga@pucp.edu.pe

In the quest for more efficient ways to protect nature, granting legal personality to the rivers has become a global legal trend in the last decades. By April 2023, approximately more than one hundred cases of officially recognized nature's rights existed worldwide, the American continent showing approximately ninety-six cases, not all of them successful. This has created an interesting tapestry of legal pluralism that takes many shapes according to several factors and contexts. Unlike Ecuador and Bolivia Peru has not recognized the subjectivity of nature in the Constitution, which has led social movements and NGOs to enforce the rights of rivers in the courts and at the municipality level. In 2021, with the support of Instituto Defensa Legal, International Rivers and Earth Law Center and the Catholic Apostolic Vicariate of Iquitos, the Kukama Huaynakana Kamatahuara Kana Federation filed an amparo lawsuit to recognize the Marañón river as a subject of rights in Peru. By mid-March 2024, a judge in Nauta issued a ruling finally recognizing that the Marañón river is holder (not subject) of rights to freely flow, to a healthy ecosystem, among others. This achievement was intended to defend the river from constant oil spills, but the State appealed the sentence. In this paper, I explore the process to recognize the Marañón river as a subject of rights in Peru to show how legal pluralism takes place as a glocal process to defend Nature.

Mystical Regimes of Order: Ritualistic Practices and Conflict Resolution in Everyday Uttarakhand

Dr. Kalindi Kokal, independent scholar, India, kalindikokal@gmail.com

Esoteric Rituals for maintenance and restoration of order are widespread in India. These rituals are more prominent among communities that live close to nature and whose lives are integrally dependent on their natural surroundings. Ideas of order and justice within these communities inevitably reflect a continuous interaction and communication with their natural surroundings. An observation of these rituals reveals how more-than-human entities including winds, natural springs, land, spirits and deities are manifested with emotions of fear, jealousy, greed and happiness, thus enabling humans to imagine them as part of a shared ecosystem. Drawing of fieldwork involving close observation of such rituals in Uttarakhand, this author asks what the practice of such rituals means for human-nature relationships. In a country like India, is the development of environmental conservation embedded in nurturing or reviving a spiritual relationship with nature where rivers can cry, and trees can talk? What does this mean for the discourse of rights and justice that continues to have a strong foothold in a scientific and rational worldview.

Alofipo So'oalo. The legally pluralist potential in human rights and indigenous standing (in) for the more-than-human world

Fleur Ramsay, Blue Ocean Law fleur@blueoceanlaw.com

This paper will argue that a number of human rights can provide standing for indigenous peoples to bring cases protecting the more-than-human world in places where custom has not been recognised in State legal systems. The presenter will discuss cultural rights, the right to a healthy environment, the right to home and privacy, the right to life and rights to freedom of expression, association and belief as providing the basis for indigenous peoples to bring claims protecting the-more-than-human. The presenter will inform her discussion with Oceanic philosophies and ontologies embedded in story, art, cultural praxis and environmental stewardship which either blur the boundaries of the human with the more-than-human, recognises a genealogical connection with the more-than-human or creates

stewardship/custodian obligations providing ample standing to bring human rights claims for the more-than-human.

Personifying Nature: Posthuman Feminist Theory to Inform and Reform Indonesia's Climate Litigation Strategy for Rights of Nature Claim

Fildza Nabila Avianti, Greenpeace Southeast Asia, fildzanabila@gmail.com; Muhammad Wildan Teddy Bintang Prakoso Has, Universitas Indonesia, wildan.teddy@gmail.com

In Indonesia, a Rights of Nature (RoN) claim has not yet been used widely in climate litigation. The Jakarta Air Pollution case found seven state officials guilty of negligence for inadequate responses to air pollution in the capital. While the landmark case emphasized rights to a healthy environment, it perpetuates the current climate litigation strategy that is still anthropocentric, regarding humans as separate from and superior to nature. This means that the current strategy largely connects the detriments of climate crisis only to humans, but not to non-human entities and natural systems. By introducing posthuman feminist theory that analyses legal personhood of 'the nature', a new strategy approach could incorporate a broader consideration of non-human perspectives. This paper illuminates the importance of collaborating posthuman feminist theory and RoN to bridge the realms of 'the nature' and law. We discuss scholarly arguments which contributed to the development of posthuman feminist theory and RoN, and the contrast to Indonesian environmental law and transnational climate litigation in practice. We then analyse several Indonesian climate cases, including the pending transnational case before the Cantonal Court of Zug—Asmania et al. vs Holcim—concerning people of the Indonesian Island of Pari and the Swiss cement company with the basis of personal rights infringement and redress for unjust harm using the posthuman theory and RoN. Finally, we propose a framework to use posthuman feminist theory and RoN in practice and what commitment they might demand of law and policy to be applied to Indonesian environmental law.

The need for ecocentrism in India's climate change conversation

Anju Anna John, University of Deusto, anju.anna.john@deusto.es

In a recent case, the Supreme Court of India recognised that that people had a fundamental right to be free from adverse impacts of climate change. However, this argument about sustainable development for the larger population of the country was pitted against the conservation of a critically endangered species. We have previously seen it, in the context of development projects. Today, there is another major development project that is set to come up in the pristine tropical rainforest of the Great Nicobar that is home to indigenous communities and houses several endemic species. In light of the 5th Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), we know that biodiversity can support efforts to reduce the negative effects of climate change. Conserving these ecosystems not only go on to prevent the extinction of endemic species, but also provide ecosystem services that are essential for human well-being. This is not new wisdom. Indigenous communities have always believed in the need to protect nature for their own survival and how the two are inextricably related. Unlike the West, India's environmental movement has its roots in struggles of the indigenous people against encroachment on their ancestral lands for their survival. Therefore, India needs to move beyond recognising the human rights impact of the climate change crisis and take on an ecocentric approach while addressing issues of environmental protection. This article would seek to make an argument based on ecocentrism and the rights of indigenous peoples against the upcoming Great Nicobar project.

Religious-Cultural Framing of Climate Change: The Role of Indic Normative Value System in Climate Action

Rajnish Saryal, associate Professor of Political Science, University Institute of Law, Panjab University Regional Centre, Ludhiana, Punjab, India, rajnishsaryal@gmail.com; rajnish@pu.ac.in

One of the major planetary challenges to the world in the twenty first century is indisputably the climate crisis. The United Nations through its various agencies like UNEP, UNFCCC and other legal instruments tried to resolve the climate crisis. The resulted international climate regime placed climate change not only in a specific legal framework but also in the normative framework that drew upon religious-nature-cultural discourses. Quite in contrast to the Kyoto Protocol of 1997, the Paris Agreement of 2015, in particular, adopted the bottom-up approach which tacitly acknowledged the plurality of normative framework within and across many societies that may effectively address climate change. In this paper, I analysed the role of Indic traditions through the religious-culture framing of climate change to explore whether or in what way this normative framing is helpful in the climate action. The paper further examined possible contestations between state law and normative framework on environmental issues in Indian society. The increased emphasis on normative approach to climate crisis indicated a deviation from the modern state law that primarily rely on secular force in the area of environmental protection. This explained that climate change was more of a behavioural issue that better fitted into the religious-cultural farming rather than just a problem of modern science and positive state law. The paper concludes that legal pluralism that focused on plurality of normative orders within and across societies provided a good framework to answer questions that arouse from the issue of climate crisis.

Panel 15

Gender Construction in Indigenous Communities from The Perspective of Legal Pluralism

Convenor: Lidwina Inge Nurtjahyo, Faculty of Law, Universitas Indonesia, lidwina.nurtjahyo@gmail.com

This panel presents the results of observing gender construction in indigenous communities and its various consequences. The problems discussed range from the issue of indigenous women's access to land and distribution of natural resource products, the meaning and protection of indigenous women's intellectual property rights, including discussions regarding women's participation in decision making regarding natural resource conflicts or access to enjoyment of natural resources. This panel is also open to discussions regarding the experiences of women in indigenous communities in terms of involvement in decision making related to cases of sexual violence. This discussion uses the lens of legal anthropology, specifically the study of legal pluralism.

Challenging the Stigma: Understanding Communities, Adat Law, and the Shifting Roles of Adat Women

Tine Suartina, Research Center for Society and Culture, National Research and Innovation Agency (BRIN), t.suartina@hotmail.com.

In confronting modernization with traditionalities, customary communities adopt strategies. Two ethnographic cases in Kasepuhan customary (*adat*) communities in Sukabumi and Lebak exemplify shifts in women's roles and centering their positions in interactions with externalities. Such responsibilities encompass both internal and external roles, as opposed to their prior, limited duties. These women, despite varying social standings within the communities, serve dual purposes: as agents of change, bridging modernity to traditional interests, facilitating communication, and fostering relationships with external parties. Concomitantly, they are trusted to maintain the enforcement of *adat* and customary values during the process of communities' exposure.

More responsibilities and recognitions remain within *communities'* rules and leaders' consent. This demonstrates how customary communities and laws can be dynamic and distinct from the notion that *adat*, or traditional communities, must have a frozen tradition to maintain their identity. In fact, communities decide parts for adaptation and resistance based on beliefs, norms, and laws first as their basic principle, filter, and boundary. For them, this is not a barrier, as belonging to the community is non-negotiable.

In this study, women's changing positions in *adat* communities are examined through the lens of legal anthropology and socio-legal viewpoints. A more comprehensive contribution will deal with refuting negative stereotypes and providing an update on the discussions held by two experts: Benda-Beckmann (1989) on how traditional communities and laws have been scapegoated as impediments of development and anti-modernization; and Scott (1998) on the need for local understandings to carry out development programs and avoid failures.

Traditional Knowledge of Indigenous Women in Community R: Diverging Paradigms between Indigenous Women, National Law, and International Law on Concepts, Threats, and Demands

Nadya Demadevina, HuMA, deademadev@gmail.com

From an international law perspective, the protection of traditional knowledge is often limited to benefit-sharing mechanisms. This reductionist approach is reflected in national legislation, which frames traditional knowledge within intellectual property rights and cultural promotion constructs. Both frameworks primarily identify "biopiracy," where external entities exploit traditional knowledge without adequate benefit-sharing, as the main threat. Indigenous women, however, view traditional knowledge holistically, as it is deeply intertwined with their daily lives. In Community R, this knowledge includes agricultural practices, rituals, traditional medicine, and weaving. For these women, weaving transcends intellectual property concepts, being integral to daily life and community traditions. Woven fabrics are vital in all ceremonies, whether worn or offered as gifts. Studies in Community R reveal a collective openness among women towards outsiders learning and commercializing their weaving patterns. This openness stems from a tradition of inter-community weaving technique exchange, fostering solidarity and kinship. Women in Community R frequently assist each other in marketing their woven products at local markets. When asked about threats to their traditional knowledge, the women uniformly identified development projects that could displace their ancestral lands as the paramount concern. Losing these lands means losing access to essential weaving materials and spaces for traditional rituals. Thus, protecting traditional knowledge requires a holistic approach that considers the concepts, threats, and demands of indigenous women across Indonesia.

Challenges in Implementing the Sexual Violence Crime Law in Indigenous Communities. A Study from a Legal Pluralism Perspective

Lidwina Inge Nurtjahyo, Faculty of Law, Universitas Indonesia, lidwina.inge@ui.ac.id

Regulations related to sexual violence in Indonesia have been regulated in 2022 through Law No. 12 of 2022 of Criminal Acts of Sexual Violence (UU TPKS). Before this Law has been stipulated, sexual violence cases have been handled based on the Criminal Law and are only referred to as moral crimes. After the TPKS Law was enacted, various socialization of these regulations was carried out to the groups and communities in the society. This includes service provider groups, women's groups, and even law enforcement officers. However, from the socialization process, input or feedback was also obtained from the socialization participants that in indigenous communities, the implementation of this Law presented a number of challenges. Firstly, in traditional communities there is a general practice that victims of sexual violence are considered to bring shame to their families and thus immediate reparation must be carried

out not for the victim but for the community who are shaken and embarrassed by the incident of violence. As a form of bringing back the harmony of the society, sometimes the authorities in the village or communities pushed the victim to marry the perpetrator to cover the shame. Families even approve of the practice. Second, in indigenous communities there may be a refusal to report the case to the police. Cases are attempted to be resolved internally. These kinds of challenges of the implementation of UU TPKS are very interesting to analyse using the perspective of legal pluralism studies and feminist legal studies.

Masculinization of Weaving Tradition in Eastern Sumba: Cultural Policy, and Gender Inequities

Mochammad Arief Wicaksono, Department of Anthropology, Universitas Indonesia, ariefwicaksono.m@gmail.com

This study explores the masculinization of traditional ikat weaving in Eastern Sumba, Indonesia—a domain historically dominated by women—and its implications through the lens of legal pluralism and cultural policy. As men increasingly take over the production and commercialization of weaving, this gender shift disrupts established roles, leading to significant socio-economic and cultural consequences. The research critically examines how cultural policies and laws, often aligned with tourism and economic gains, tend to marginalize women by prioritizing market-driven objectives over the preservation of gender-equitable cultural practices. These policies, while promoting the global recognition and commercialization of Sumbanese textiles, frequently overlook the traditional roles of women weavers, leading to their disenfranchisement. By analyzing the interplay between local customary laws, national legislation, and international trade regulations, this study highlights the legal and cultural frameworks that perpetuate gender inequities. The research underscores the need for more inclusive cultural policies that recognize and protect the contributions of women within indigenous communities, ensuring that economic development does not come at the expense of gender justice. This inquiry into the legal and cultural dynamics of weaving in Eastern Sumba offers a critical perspective on the challenges and opportunities for indigenous women in the face of global economic pressures, calling for a reevaluation of cultural laws that better align with the principles of equity and cultural preservation.

Panel 16

Religious family laws and legal pluralities

Convenor: Waheeda Amien, University of Cape Town, waheeda.amien@uct.ac.za

Countries are governed either by so-called secular laws or one or other religious (and/or customary) laws. Where secular law is the governing legal system, religious laws tend to operate within communities, with or without official state recognition. In these circumstances, religious bodies regulate the religious personal and family laws within their communities. Many also establish religious-based arbitration forums to manage disputes, especially within the personal and family law arenas. Where a religious law is the predominant legal system within a country, divergent or alternative interpretations of that religious law and other religious laws may be unofficially operative in the country's communities. Pluralism therefore manifests through official (state) and unofficial (non-state) laws permeating societies. This panel seeks to explore multiple themes relating to religious family laws including: The relationship between state and non-state laws and their implications for the fundamental rights of marginalised members within religious communities such as women's rights, children's rights, and the rights of LGBTQI+ people. How the management and implementation of religious-based arbitration forums affect individual and group rights? And the challenges that arise from the lived experiences of those located within religious-based communities, whether they are state regulated or not. Papers are invited to address the above and other related themes.

Between the ‘official’ and ‘unofficial’: Muslim Women’s Experience of Marriage in Post-Catholic Malta

Ibtisam Sadegh, University of Malta Ibtisam.sadegh@um.edu.mt

Over the past fifty years, Malta’s matrimonial legal system has transitioned from a purely religious marriage system, which ostensibly recognized all religious marriages equally, to a civil marriage system, and finally to the present dualistic Secular-Religious regulation, which recognizes both civil and religious marriages. Despite substantial recent reforms, Canon law continues to influence the understanding of marriage in Malta, with civil marriages heavily dependent on canonical principles. Moreover, although Maltese marriage law has shifted from a colonial Church-State dualism to the current “post-Catholic” state, in practice, only church marriages are granted legal effect, leaving Muslim marriages celebrated in Malta unrecognized. Within the broader socio-political context, Muslim women are often perceived as victims of a patriarchal religious system that oppresses them, particularly through marriage. Drawing on multiple semi-structured interviews with Muslim women who have celebrated Muslim marriages in Malta, this paper explores their experiences and examines their agency as they navigate the discriminatory State framework and the expectations of their families and communities, whilst also seeking some form of recognition of their marriages. Additionally, the paper investigates the role of the Imam in Malta’s only Mosque, who views his function as protecting women’s rights and in the process, facilitates the inclusion of new marriage practices among Maltese Muslim couples. In so doing, the paper sheds light on the various strategies employed by the local Imam and the Muslim women in Malta in response to the present Marriage law system, as they navigate the complex interplay between what is considered ‘unofficial’ and ‘official’ within State and religious laws.

Contradictions of mandatory wills for heirs of different religions

Dinda Keumala, Setiyono, Universitas Trisakti, Indonesia, dinda.k@trisakti.ac.id, setiyono@trisakti.ac.id

Inheritance law in Indonesia is still pluralistic, as simultaneously three different inheritance laws still apply, namely Customary Inheritance Law, Islamic Inheritance Law, and Western Inheritance Law. A person can become an heir because of blood relations, marital relations, and through a will. Islamic Inheritance Law prohibits interfaith heirs from inheriting, but in practice judges’ rulings provide mandatory wills for interfaith heirs on the grounds of a sense of justice. The problem at this writing is the existence of mandatory will arrangements for heirs of different religions and how the implementation of mandatory wills should be carried out. This type of research is normative and descriptive with secondary data collection carried out by literature review. Data analysis is qualitative with conclusions drawn from deductive methods. The result of this research is that in the Compilation of Islamic Law, there has never been a mandatory will for heirs of different religions. The execution of a mandatory will should still be based on the provisions stipulated in the Compilation of Islamic Law.

Islamic Feminism in the MENA Region and the CEDAW Convention: Exploring Intersections and Activism.

Mona Hemieda, Coelho fellow Loyola Law School, Los Angeles, monahemieda2017@gmail.com

This research examines the phenomenon of Islamic feminism in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region, with a focus on Egypt, Morocco, and Tunisia. The study delves into the definition of Islamic feminism and explores how Islamic feminists engage with politics, law, and international conventions, particularly the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW). The research aims to investigate the Islamic feminist movement and its role in effecting changes in family laws within Muslim-majority countries. It seeks to understand whether Islamic

feminists solely rely on religious principles or if they employ diverse forms of activism to improve women's positions and conditions in society. Through a comprehensive analysis of scholarly literature, legal documents, and case studies, this study will shed light on the strategies employed by Islamic feminists in the MENA region. It will explore how they navigate the complexities of religious interpretations, cultural norms, and patriarchal structures to advocate for gender equality and women's rights. Furthermore, this research abstract will examine the extent to which Islamic feminists are actively seeking to enact international conventions tailored to the specific contexts and needs of Muslim-majority countries. By analysing existing initiatives and discourses within the Islamic feminist movement, the study aims to uncover whether there is a collective push for the development and implementation of conventions that address the unique challenges faced by women in these countries. The research will employ a qualitative approach, utilizing a combination of in-depth interviews, document analysis, and comparative analysis of legal frameworks. The findings will contribute to the existing body of knowledge on Islamic feminism, offering insights into the strategies, challenges, and achievements of Islamic feminists in the MENA region.

Trapped between legal systems: Russian Jewish women and Divorce in early-20th century France

Geraldine Gudefin, Independent Scholar, geraldine.gudefin@gmail.com

At the turn of the 20th century, France received thousands of Jewish women who had left their hometowns in tsarist Russia in search of greater security and prosperity. Given that these women had left an autocratic regime in which Jews faced systemic discrimination and violence in favor of a liberal democracy known for birthing Jewish Emancipation, historians have generally depicted this migration positively, namely as an opportunity for Jewish women to liberate themselves from the oppression of the state, patriarchy and gendered-based religious discrimination. My paper focuses on family law in France to tell a radically different story. It suggests instead that international migration exposed Russian Jewish women to multiple legal systems of family law (including French private international law, tsarist law and rabbinical law) and that in doing so, it left them with little to no protection against abusive husbands. In particular, I examine the following paradox: in the early 20th century, divorce was allowed by both French and rabbinical law, yet French courts prevented non-naturalized Jewish immigrants from confessional legal systems (especially Russia) from dissolving their marriages. The French jurisprudence on divorce proved dramatic for Russian Jewish women seeking to sever the marital bond. Permanently trapped in their marriages, these women could also find themselves stripped of child custody and spousal support. This paper thus raises broader questions about the ways in which the intersection of multiple legal regimes could (and still does) hurt women on the move.

The Dissolution of Hindu Marriages in South African Law: A Critique of the Religious Entanglement Doctrine from a Human Rights Perspective

Devina Perumal, University of Cape Town, South Africa, divyp1962@gmail.com

Hindu marriages are not recognized as legally valid for the purpose of divorce in South Africa. A Hindu marriage that complies with the requirements for a civil marriage, enjoys dual validity. In such event, the civil marriage can be dissolved by a secular divorce order in terms of the Divorce Act, but the secular divorce order does not free the spouses from the bonds of their 'purely religious' Hindu marriage because Hinduism as practiced by South African Hindus prohibits divorce. Consequently, access to divorce remains an intractable challenge for spouses in those marriages, and have been particularly prejudicial to Hindu women. In this regard, South African courts are constrained by the common law doctrine of religious entanglement, which prohibits the adjudication of disputes that turn on religion. This paper advances a critique of the entanglement doctrine with reference to the case of *Singh v Ramparsad* 2007 (3) SA 445 (D). Premised on the argument that the entanglement doctrine subverts the full adjudication

of matters where human rights are in issue, the author makes out a case for how South African courts can assume jurisdiction, as opposed to adjudicative abstention in matrimonial disputes that turn on religious doctrine. This is done with reference to the human rights jurisprudence developed by the Indian Supreme Court, which seeks to align personal laws with constitutional principles of substantive gender equality and human dignity.

Legal Gone Wrong: A Case Study of Present-Day Lebanon

Fatima Dhanani, SOAS, University of London, fdhanani@gmail.com

Lebanon's personal status laws are governed by the 18 officially recognized religious communities and 15 courts of law. Each of these religious groups has the constitutional right to manage their own personal status laws. This vast diversity in religious practices and legal systems has significant implications for state and non-state laws, group rights, and especially women's rights. My recent ethnographic fieldwork in Beirut in 2023 highlighted the challenges of how legal pluralism has manifested in practice as a colonial project since the French mandate through the codification process. The lived experiences of my participants demonstrated the additional agency women employ to protect themselves within a patriarchal system. Furthermore, Lebanon lacks civil laws to govern matters of private family law. Consequently, individuals and minority groups within religious communities have no recourse outside their religious traditions, showcasing the power dynamics between the state and religious authorities. Civil society groups in Lebanon, particularly feminist activist groups, are collaborating with NGOs to advocate for a unified personal status code that protects women without violating the sanctity of religious connections among the Lebanese people. In effect, they are working to uphold key principles of the Lebanese constitution. In this paper, I will present examples from my ethnographic fieldwork on women's challenges with legal pluralism in Lebanon. Additionally, I will examine the difficulties posed by the sectarian system, the crucial role of civil society organizations in a failed state, and the underlying tensions between politics and power that sustain the current system.

The Effects of Non-Marriage on Muslim Communities: Critical Postcolonial Perspectives

Dr. Zainab Naqvi, Manchester Metropolitan University (UK), z.naqvi@mmu.ac.uk

In this paper I argue that the English judicial concept of non-marriage racializes and Orientalizes minoritized Muslim communities and their marriages. Applying a critical postcolonial lens, I show how the development of non-marriage has been influenced by colonial racializing attitudes towards marriage. This has led to its application in racist and orientalist ways to demean and other Muslim marriage practices. My analysis exposes three patterns in the judicial discourse in this area. First, that the courts emphasize "English (Christian) marriage" and its supposed hallmarks when deciding if a ceremony is non-existent; second that judgments foreground the technical, formal aspects of the law obscuring the use of personal judicial opinions which are orientalist. Finally, the application of this concept to playacting, sham and forced marriages at the same time as legitimate Muslim marriage practices is demeaning and insulting to the already marginalized communities that practice them.

Navigating Islamic and African Customary Family Law for Reverted African Muslims in South Africa

Fatima Essop, independent researcher, fessop@icloud.com

South African has been described as having a deep legal pluralism approach to its multiple systems of laws, with the common and African customary laws embodying official legal pluralism, whilst the

unofficial legal systems (e.g. Hindu, Jewish, and Muslim law) embody ‘deep’ legal pluralism. The intersection of Islamic family law and African customary family law presents unique challenges for African Muslims who have reverted to Islam. This paper explores the complexities faced by reverts in negotiating critical aspects of family life, particularly focusing on the practices of mahr (Islamic bridal gift) and lobola (African bride price), as well as the institution of polygamy. African Muslims who have reverted to Islam often find themselves at the crossroads of two distinct legal and cultural frameworks. Mahr, as stipulated by Islamic law, serves as a symbol of respect and responsibility towards the bride. Conversely, lobola, rooted in African traditions, signifies a familial transaction aimed at solidifying bonds between families. The obligation to fulfil both these practices can lead to financial and social strains, exacerbating the reverts' struggles to integrate their new religious identity with their cultural heritage. Polygamy, sanctioned under both Islamic and African customary law, further complicates the landscape. While both legal systems permit multiple marriages, the underlying motivations, regulations, and societal perceptions can differ significantly. Islamic law imposes stringent conditions to ensure fairness and justice among wives, while African customary law's approach may vary widely across different ethnic groups. This paper delves into these multifaceted challenges, drawing on case studies and legal analyses to highlight the potential strategies reverts may employ to reconcile these divergent legal expectations. It underscores the necessity for a pluralistic legal approach that respects and integrates both Islamic and African customary norms, fostering a harmonious coexistence that supports the cultural and religious identity of African Muslim reverts.

Panel 17

Author meets Readers of According to Aboriginal Law ...

Convenor: Agnes Schreiner, University of Amsterdam, a.t.m.schreiner@uva.nl

Agnes Schreiner, from the University of Amsterdam, The Netherlands and specialized in social and cultural legal studies, has just before the pandemic finished the bilingual book *According to Aboriginal Law ... /Volgens Aboriginal recht ...* (May 2019). The core question is what do Australian indigenous people mean when they address law. In order to approach this topic, she uses concepts and ideas beyond regular legal anthropology, such as the Gestalt Switch, the mnemotechnics of the analogy, the art of appearing and disappearing. In this panel she hopes for a vivid exchange of ideas and research results with fellow colleagues in the fields of the legal anthropology in general and in that of the Australian Indigenous Peoples Studies in particular. She found a reader in Ad Borsboom, the author of a short review in the *Oceania Newsletter* No. 95, September 2019. Borsboom concludes: “This book is an intellectual challenging and inspiring piece of work. It combines a thorough knowledge of both Legal Anthropology and Anthropology in general with accurate analytic observations of films, documentaries and exhibitions. It pictures the almost two incompatible perceptions of relation to land in particular and of cultural ways of thinking in general. The very last sentence of the book says it all: “the ultimate consequence that a legal (Western) system wanting to offer space within it ranks to Aboriginal law will not know what it invites. But perhaps a book like this will be a valuable contribution to overcome the biggest hurdles.” This author meets reader session invites readers for a discussion on this book. The author can provide readers with the manuscript.

Participants:

- Bart Jansen
- David Zammit
- Tbd

Panel 18

Round Table: Transformative Power of teaching customary law (new style)

Convenors: Rikardo Simarmata, Tody S.J. Utama (Gadjah Mada University Yogyakarta) and Jacqueline Vel, Adriaan Bedner (Van Vollenhoven Institute for Law, Governance and Society, Leiden Law School, Leiden University). Email organizers: t.s.j.utama@law.leidenuniv.nl and j.a.c.vel@law.leidenuniv.nl

Customary law is often associated with traditional communities whose members live in relative isolation from the world, but in present-day multi-cultural societies it has become a mix of traditions and articulates with state and religious law. Customary (living) law is an important element of local legal pluralism that contributes to how people regulate their local societies, but also how they deal with threats to their livelihoods imposed by forces outside their own communities. Defence against problems caused by climate change, environmental destruction, geo-political tensions and violent conflict calls for effective legal tools, also at the local level of villages and city neighbourhoods. These new global challenges create a situation in which customary rules might only be relevant or effective if adjusted to the changing circumstances. This round table invites participants for a discussion on new ways of teaching about customary law and local legal pluralism. As the title of the conference promises, the papers will present results of research on “the transformative power of legal pluralism”. What would be the translations of insights of such research to legal education? The organizers of this round table are involved in a Project on Innovation of Teaching Customary Law (PINTAL) at Law Schools in Indonesia. Up to the present nearly all customary law courses are taught in a doctrinal way that resonates the colonial origin of the lawyer’s version of customary law. Meanwhile law graduates need to be well-prepared for their professional careers in the modern setting of legal pluralism. We invite participants to reflect on education innovations concerning customary law, for example addressing how to teach about:

- Customary law embedded in legal pluralism as living law,
- (new) customary defence mechanisms against new global challenges, and
- The shape of articulation between customary law and the national state legal system?

The round table seeks contributions that stimulate international comparisons. We invite you to write a one-page explanation on your proposal for innovating teaching customary law in preparation for this round table.

Teaching a dual legal system: A South African perspective

Fatima Osman, University of Cape Town, Fatima.Osman@uct.ac.za

The South African Constitution recognizes customary law as a legal system whose force and validity derives from the Constitution and is subject only to the Constitution. This contribution explores three key challenges in teaching customary law at a South African law school in the post Constitutional dispensation. First, while the courts and legislature continually espouse the importance and value of customary law, the legislature has been slow in enacting legislation in key areas such as traditional leadership and traditional courts, with policy often clouded by the political agenda of the time. Furthermore, legislative and judicial interventions often import the common law to regulate customary law matters. The result is that what needs to be taught is a complex legal framework (layered with political concerns) which often contradicts the Constitutional Court’s rhetoric regarding the importance and protection of customary law. Secondly, the lack of empirical research into living customary law practices means that law schools are often forced to perpetuate official, outdated and stereotypical accounts of customary law that may not accord with lived practices. The reality is that practical research constraints often severely circumscribe the curricula of law schools. Finally, the historical, systemic subjugation of customary law persists in South Africa today and permeates the manner in which customary law is received and considered useful for a successful legal career.

Experiential-based Teaching of Customary Law (Adat Law) in Indonesia

Rival Ahmad, Jentera Law School, Jakarta, Indonesia, rivalga@gmail.com

As noted by scholars across generations, including Simarmata¹ and Soekanto², teaching of customary law is dominated by positivistic and doctrinaire methods. As a result, students' understanding of customary law is more static and inferior, or merely an addition to complement their technical skills and knowledge. This reduces the knowledge and imagination of prospective law graduates to see the transformational power of customary law in facing the current difficult times. Various suggestions for studying and teaching customary law in an interdisciplinary manner have been put forward, but it still needs to be supplemented with comprehensive teaching methods considering that customary law is not just doctrine and ritual, but practice, ideas, resilience and meaning-making, in a full-of -challenges dynamic living space. In the development of socio-legal studies, customary law studies have also reached out to epistemological criticism. The perspectives of decolonization, more-than-human-world, multispecies justice, ecolaw, posthuman law, and so on provide a more radical position for customary law, especially in the practice of legal reform.³ The study of customary law is seen as a knowledge strategy that dismantles not only the legal definition, but the mainstream definition of society. The study of customary law has given a respected place to nonhumans, including ancestors, abiotic objects and other living creatures in socio-legal relations. Customary law also challenges the dominance-orientation of human society in discussing justice, sustainability and the viability of life on earth. The need to teach customary law in a new way is not only important, but necessary to begin to anchor customary law in its basic relationship with the society in which it is lived, as well as in its relationship with law reform processes at supralocal, national and global levels, in order to respond to challenges and natural and socio-political crisis. This proposal is based on pedagogy which believes that there are at least four ways of knowing in an effective learning process, namely: cognition, emotion, intuition and somatics.⁴ Experiential-based learning as a learning method proposes a learning route that optimizes this way of knowing: experiencing, elaborating, analysing, practicing and reflecting. Practically, this learning method will invite students to directly experience community life where customary law is lived and developed. Then, together with the local community, students will elaborate the important things that underlie the birth and development of the principles, values, goals and process of working of local norms in that location. Then actively analyse how these norms are placed in practice and their relationship with theories, principles and methods that are related and relevant to their existence. Then in the next stage, study through the practice/actions in cases that are or have the potential to occur in the field. In the final stage, students together with local communities reflect on what has happened, how it is interpreted by the community and what consequences it has for the continuity of customary law and the lives of the people who live it. The challenges of this method are time management, location selection, community preparation to receive students and lecturers, readiness of lecturers, as well as technical and operational preparation.

Transformative Role of Private International law in Teaching and Studying Legal Pluralism

Zixuan Yang, Hamburg University/MPI Hamburg, Germany, yang@mpipriv.de

The "Inter-systemic conflicts law" proposed by the German scholar Teubner triggered 21st century private international law scholars to explore and construct the discipline in the field of transnational governance. For Teubner, "inter-systemic conflict law" mainly deals with conflicts between the supranational norms of functionally differentiated social sub-systems in a global society, manifesting itself in the interaction or overlap of different norms in the transnational arena, and is quite different from the traditional private international law resolving conflicts of law between sovereign states. However, the transcendence of supranational regimes over the legal order of sovereign states, as observed by Teubner, reveal the plurality

and dynamics of normative production in the context of globalisation. The resulting multi-layered network of norms acts on the international legal order horizontally (between sovereign states), vertically (between sovereign states and supranational regimes), and obliquely (between different norms at different levels). Against this background, private international law, which originated in the 19th century private law conflicts between nation-states, has ushered in a new theoretical and institutional revolution. Teubner's conceptual borrowing from private international law (conflict-of-law) is not occasional. The interplay between legal pluralism and private international law long existed throughout different times and regions. This could date back to Eugen Ehrlich's work and interest in private international law's pre-modern history in Europe.² For many scholars, private international law emerged while dealing with conflict of customary laws among Germanic tribals or city-states in medieval Italy.³ Codifications of European nation states in the 19th century represented the transformation of private law as well as the pattern of public and private international law. In comparison, Asian laws from the 19th century have still been perceived as the classical case for legal pluralism with regard to the coexistence of diverse local customs and religions. This pluralism evolved with mixed historical characteristics of inner-imperialism and extra-colonialism influence. Due to the deeply-rooted religions, customs and traditions in the local society, customary laws were retained and reserved to strike the balance between local governance and legal modernization. But when it comes to regional or global context, how to describe or handle these local customs posed challenges onto modern lawyers. Here, I argue that private international law provided the toolbox to describe, adapt and apply local customary laws. First, presumption of equal legal systems enabled local customs to be taken into consideration without prejudices. Second, classical patterns of territorial and personal application of norms have much more universal potentials in both domestic and foreign-related cases. Therefore, if we adopt a broader understanding upon private international law, much more potentials can be explored for its role in the pluralistic thinking and handling of interactive legal systems.

ADDITIONAL DISCUSSANTS:

- Sartika Intaning Pradhani, Faculty of Law, Universitas Gadjah Mada, Indonesia
- Janine Ubink, Van Vollenhoven Institute for Law, Governance and society, Leiden University